

Project acronym: COSMIC
Project title: The COntribution of Social Media In Crisis management
Grant number: 312737
Programme: Seventh Framework Programme – Security Research
Objective: SEC-2012.6.1-3
Contract type: Coordination and support action
Start date of project: 01 April 2013
Duration: 24 months
Website: www.cosmic-project.eu

Deliverable D3.1.2: Final report on the use of emerging technologies in crisis situations

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Dissemination level: Public
Deliverable type: Final
Version: 1
Submission date: 31st October 2014

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Change Records

Issue	Date	Description	Author (Company)
0.1	22/09/13	First draft	ED
0.2	23/09/13	Draft contribution	RUN
0.3	26/09/13	Revision and finalisation of text	RUN
0.4	27/09/13	Revision and finalisation of text	ED
0.5	30/10/2013	Editing and expansion of chapter 5	ED, RUN
0.6	31/10/2013	Revision and finalisation	ED

DRAFT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is the final version of Deliverable D3.1 of the COSMIC project, released as D3.1.2. It provides results in the analysis of emerging communication technologies in support of crisis management.

New communication technologies and social media have greatly expanded the overall scope of communication in crisis management, because of several new synergetic factors, including: access to communication technology, richer communication modalities, communication occurring in public, and data exhaust. Therefore, the scope of emerging communication technologies, and social media and applications, encompasses: intentional acts of communication; unintentional acts of communication; handling information as its recipient; and accessing and analysing public information as a third party. We provide a list of 27 specific emerging technology areas and application areas that are relevant according to this scope. These include: citizen journalism, cloud, crowdsourcing, data mining, big data, decision support, open data, Internet of Things, wearable sensors and others. These are all examined and appraised for their possible role in social media aided crisis management.

New and emerging technologies, which can generally offer significant help in combating crises, also entail a variety of risks, such as those to individuals' privacy and sense of identity; the correct allocation of responsibility in evolving crises; the possibility of information overload; the potential of creating conflicts of interest among responders; and the general possibility of producing unintended, negative consequences even when the initial aim is crisis management.

Aided by emerging technology areas, as analysed in the present document, social media are transforming many aspects of crisis management. They contribute to the openness, fairness and quickness of communication during a crisis and can be used in a variety of ways: making diagnoses of vulnerabilities in systems and infrastructures (in preparation for crises); facilitating and simplifying search and rescue missions (during a crisis); and enhancing control and community connectedness (including the recovery stages after a crisis). In addition to their use by individuals, social media are also being exploited in large crisis management projects, in a manner similar to those of NASA style "mission control centres", for monitoring and responding to the generation of massive stream of media messages.

1 INTRODUCTION

This is the final version of Deliverable D3.1 of the COSMIC project, released as D3.1.2. It provides results in the analysis of emerging communication technologies in support of crisis management. It discusses the topic of emerging technologies and focuses on: a preliminary analysis of social media trends; identifying a broad variety of emerging communication technologies with significance to crisis management; and analysing a selection of the identified emerging technologies.

The rapid evolution of communication technologies is changing crisis management^{1,2,3}. The COSMIC project has already discussed current uses of communication technologies in crisis management, especially in Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2. In this document, we address emerging technologies that have begun to impact crisis management or that are expected to impact crisis management, with emphasis on future potential.

In Section 2, partners discuss what constitutes a relevant emerging communication technology in the context of an evolving crisis. We show that a very broad range of technologies is highly relevant and important. We identify 27 specific technologies and we categorise them with respect to core features of relevance to crisis management.

In Section 3, partners discuss the emerging risks, for crisis management and beyond, that arise in the context of emerging communication technologies. Despite their great potential for positive effects, these technologies also pose a variety of threats, from invading our privacy, to potentially influencing our sense of our own identity.

In Section 4, partners discuss emerging social media applications. Social media are being used increasingly and with a constantly growing level of importance in the context of crisis management. Here, we consider relevant social media trends, the behaviours of users, and the changing role of social media in preparation for a crisis, during the crisis and in response to a crisis.

In Section 5, partners individually analyse the emerging technologies that have been identified as important in the context of crisis management. The technologies are discussed in general, specific technical background is provided along with evidence of their relevance and finally the potential technical impact in crisis management is discussed.

¹ Ng, Vanessa Mei-Yee. *Evolving technologies for disaster planning in US Cities*. Diss. Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2011.

² Humanitarianism in the Network Age: Including World Humanitarian Data and Trends 2012, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 2013.

³ “Software that helps populations cope with crises”,
<http://www2.technologyreview.com/TR35/Profile.aspx?TRID=947>

2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOMAIN AND SCOPE OF EMERGING COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT

New communication technologies and social media have greatly expanded the overall scope of communication in crisis management, because of several new synergetic factors:

- Greater access to communication technology, particularly access for all and at any time and place through affordable mobile telephony
- More and richer communication modalities, including: voice and video communication between pairs or groups; communication through the Web and including multimedia content; and the ability to share sensor readings from mobile devices, ranging from geographical location to temperature and air pressure
- Communication occurring in public, especially including public posts on social media and other Web resources
- The “digital footprint” or “data exhaust”^{4,5,6} consisting of information generated as a side-effect of users’ activities, which is an indirect form of communication (comparable to body language as another indirect form of communication, but here in the context of ICT)

The first two factors contribute to a constantly increasing volume of communication.

The last two factors create an environment where it is not enough for the direct recipient of any communication to be responsible for handling it. Rather, vast amounts of useful information are available either publicly, or at least beyond the scope of the activity that generated it in the first place. Indeed, much of this information communicates facts about people, without its creation necessarily being consciously intended as an act of communication – similarly to body language. The information is published in free-access communication media, such as publicly accessible social media content, or is available to service providers, such as mobile telecoms who can collect location data for their subscribers, or search engines who can collect and analyse searches and clicks on results.

For example, we can imagine the following scenario. There is a sudden peak in searches for the keyword “flood”. Furthermore, the first few search results that the search engine provides are general-purpose background, such as an encyclopaedia article about floods, but a lower-ranked result is a current article about preparing for a specific, imminent flood threat. If the search engine provider observes a majority of searchers clicking on the article about preparation, this provides valuable information. A specific behaviour involving paying attention to flood preparation can be observed, and measured, through the searching activity of users, and their choices of which results to click on. However, the analysis and interpretation of such data is often a very challenging problem. For instance, in this scenario, are people learning about flood preparation “enough”?

Therefore, the scope of emerging communication technologies, and social media and applications, encompasses:

- Intentional acts of communication, with examples including voice calls, and text messages on social media
- Unintentional acts of communication, with examples including messages on publicly accessible social media accounts, and service usage information

⁴ O’Hara, Kieron, Mischa M. Tuffield, and Nigel Shadbolt. "Lifelogging: Privacy and empowerment with memories for life." *Identity in the Information Society* 1.1 (2008): 155-172.

⁵ “The data deluge”, *The Economist*, Feb 25th 2010, <http://www.economist.com/node/15579717>

⁶ “Data, data everywhere”, *The Economist*, Feb 25th 2010, <http://www.economist.com/node/15557443>

- Handling information as its recipient, with examples including individuals’ need to prioritise urgent safety messages, and organisations’ need to operate of a helpline during a crisis
- Accessing and analysing public information as a third party, with examples including the analysis of patterns appearing in social media posts, and analysis of clickstreams

Finally, the scope of emerging communication technologies and, media and applications also encompasses any specific crisis management technologies with a communications component.

Thus, a large and varied set of technologies is relevant for study in this deliverable. The following table summarises the Emerging Technology Areas and Application Areas that are discussed in detail in the document.

Table 1 below shows a summary of the emerging technology areas and application areas described in more detail in this document. For each technology or application area, two categories of relevance are indicated at the left side of the table:

- Relevance to the communication workflow
 - Sensing: relevance to the information source, including intentional transmission of information with the intention of communicating as well as any relevant kind of unintended communication
 - Deciding: relevance to the decision making process that forms a part of communication flows, such as deciding how to prioritise information being communicated
 - Acting: relevance to communicating as an action in response to a crisis, such as sending alerts, and also to the communication capabilities of the emerging technologies, which are necessary or useful as part of crisis management actions, such as a rescue robot’s capability to communicate or interact with any survivors it may encounter
 - Managing: relevance to management of communication processes, for example distributing limited computational resources to different digital communication tools
- Specific media involved⁷
 - New communications technologies
 - Social media

The ✓ symbol in the table indicates relevance, while the ● symbol is also used to indicate a lesser, but still important, degree of relevance.

Each of the technologies listed in **Table 1** is discussed in section 5 of the present document, which describes the technology and assesses its role in communications for crisis management.

⁷ see Deliverable D2.1 of the COSMIC project

Table 1: Emerging technology areas and application areas influencing crisis management communications

Sensing	Deciding	Acting	Managing	New CT	Social M.	Emerging Technology Area or Application Area
✓			✓	✓	✓	1 citizen journalism
•	•	•	•	✓		2 cloud
✓		•			✓	3 crowdsourcing
✓	✓				✓	4 data mining and big data
	✓			✓	•	5 decision support
				•	✓	6 e-inclusion & e-accountability
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		7 early warning systems
	✓		✓	✓	✓	8 epidemiology and prediction
	✓			✓	✓	9 integration of heterogeneous data
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	10 internet of things
✓	✓	✓	•	✓	✓	11 mobile eHealth
		✓	✓		✓	12 natural language technologies
✓	•	•	•	✓	✓	13 open data
✓				✓		14 “organic” or smartphone sensor networks
✓	✓			✓	✓	15 pattern analysis and machine intelligence
✓	✓				✓	16 profiling social media users
✓		✓		✓	✓	17 reporting and alerts services
		✓		✓		18 robots and drones
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	19 secure communications and trustworthy ICT
✓				✓		20 sensor infrastructures inc. satellite, surveillance & environmental sensors
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		21 smart cities and smart transportation
	✓		✓		✓	22 social media governance
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	23 tools for the mediation between governments and citizens
✓	✓					24 tools for transparency and accountability
✓		✓			✓	25 user generated content & ICT for creativity and expression
	✓			✓	✓	26 visualisation – information vis., knowledge vis., visual analytics
✓					✓	27 wearable sensors and sensors integrated in mobile communication devices

Key: ✓ major relevance
• additional relevance

3 RISKS, CONCERNS AND ETHICAL ISSUES

The technologies discussed in Section 5, below, offer significant tools for the improvement of crisis management. Nevertheless, they also entail a variety of risks, raising concern about their usage and often posing ethical dilemmas when crisis management effectiveness is traded off against factors such as privacy. In this Section, we briefly present six important risks, concerns and ethical issues that need to be kept in mind when assessing Emerging Technology Areas and Application Areas with relevance to crisis management.

3.1 PRIVACY

Self-presentation and self-disclosure are an intrinsic feature of social media, which thus intrinsically pose privacy concerns⁸. In many contexts, such as the case of data exhaust discussed above, people reveal information about themselves unintentionally, or potentially unintentionally, which again raises serious privacy concerns. This is indeed also the case in the technically simple scenario where users voluntarily make their communications fully public; such choices may have unintentional consequences, such as later embarrassment or worse, and may come to be regretted by users who can no longer reverse such choices.

The issues above are relevant regardless of the presence of a crisis. Indeed, there is a trade-off between relaxing of privacy restrictions before a crisis occurs, and information that will be already available to individuals and organisations to use in the context of crisis management when a crisis does materialise.

Specifically during a crisis, the information that is likely to be communicated is of an especially sensitive nature, addressing for instance issues such as health and vulnerabilities. For example, when a citizen calls an emergency helpline such as 911, confidentiality is expected, however, if a citizen Tweets for help, confidentiality is forsaken. Revelations made publicly in a social media based cry for help may subsequently remain public.

The risks of violating privacy are currently a topic of debate in communities analysing and assessing social media, although the current trend is for their business exploitation potential to tip the balance away from privacy⁹. However, from an ethical point of view, crisis management offers a less-debatable argument against safeguarding privacy: by sharing our personal information abundantly, we may be helping to save lives – in some cases, our own. Although this argument is certainly important, the increasing difficulty of defending privacy is an important threat.

⁸ Kaplan, Andreas M., and Michael Haenlein. "Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media." *Business horizons* 53.1 (2010): 59-68.

⁹ for example, see the above-referenced articles "The data deluge", "Data, data everywhere", and "Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media."

Figure 1: Infographic on privacy in Social media¹⁰

¹⁰ <http://www.mdgadvertising.com/blog/wp-content/uploads/2012/02/the-sad-state-of-social-media-privacy-infographic.png>

3.2 IDENTITY

Communication is an important mechanism for human beings, and our experiences of communication affect us deeply, for example influencing our very sense of our own identity^{11,12,13}. Crisis management goes beyond communication in an abstract sense, and integrates communication into practical action: an external agent takes charge of our actions, potentially even our lives, during a period of danger, learns as much about us as possible, and manages our behaviour in response to the danger. This, of course, is a tremendously valuable service, precisely because we are receiving aid to defend our property, health, or life. Nevertheless, as we build mechanisms capable of guiding our behaviour in ever more finely targeted and more subtle ways, we should also be aware that by placing ourselves in the power of these tools, we may be allowing them to define us.

Figure 2: “Who am I?”¹⁴

3.3 RESPONSIBILITY

One emerging property of the communication technologies discussed in this document is that they result, in many cases, in non-deterministic behaviours of the human actors involved. For example, when a citizen in need makes a call to an emergency number, such as 911, the response is intended to follow a deterministic workflow; however, when a citizen posts an urgent plea for help on social media, it could provoke an immediate and effective response¹⁵, or a late or ineffective response, or even no response at all. During Superstorm Sandy, the New York Fire Department initially instructed people not to tweet emergency calls, however it subsequently made excellent use of Twitter when 911 was overwhelmed with too many calls, and Twitter conveyed urgent messages more effectively¹⁶. While these examples

¹¹ Yannopoulos, Angelos, Vassiliki Andronikou, and Theodora Varvarigou. "Behavioural biometric profiling and ambient intelligence." *Profiling the European Citizen*. Springer Netherlands, 2008. 89-109.

¹² Andronikou, Vassiliki, Angelos Yannopoulos, and Theodora Varvarigou. "Biometric profiling: opportunities and risks." *Profiling the European Citizen*. Springer Netherlands, 2008. 131-145.

¹³ Gutwirth, Serge, and Mireille Hildebrandt. "Profiling the European Citizen." Springer, 2008.

¹⁴ <http://comuq.wordpress.com/2011/09/07/google-who-am-i/>

¹⁵ e.g. "Injured Biker Leigh Fazzina Rescued By Twitter", http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2010/08/03/leigh-fazzina-injured-bik_n_669175.html

¹⁶ <http://news.yahoo.com/blogs/ticket/meet-fdny-one-womantwitter-response-team-guiding-141143449.html>

illustrate that social media can be of value in a crisis situation, the scenarios do raise the question of allocating formal responsibility.

3.4 INFORMATION OVERLOAD

Data sources including open data initiatives, crowdsourcing and social media generate or provide vast quantities of data. A resulting risk is information overload¹⁷ – there may simply be too much information to process, and human responders may become confused, may overlook the more important information, or may spend too much time or effort analysing data rather than acting in response to a crisis. Some of the technologies and applications described in this document are relevant precisely because they address this particular risk, however the problem remains important.

3.5 CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

When for-profit organisations develop general-purpose assets that can be useful in the case of – but are not exclusively used for – crisis management, and when funds or effort intended for dealing with a crisis are used to improve these assets, a conflict of interests is present. For example, if a commercial map provider provides map assets for free during the response to a crisis, and solicits a crowdsourcing effort to enrich the map with important information about the region in question, the results may include a positive contribution to mitigating an ongoing crisis, but also a permanent improvement to the commercial map through the crowdsourced work. The contributions of for-profit organisations to crisis management are often very valuable, e.g. Google Crisis Map¹⁸, but awareness of any potential conflict of interests is also important, any may help to ensure companies avoid making a direct effort to profit from a crisis.

Figure 3: “Crowdsourcing: a new idea for innovating!”¹⁹. But could it be also a new idea for exploiting volunteers, who respond to needs arising due to a major crisis, for private gain?

¹⁷ Daniel Stauffacher, Sanjana Hattotuwa and Barbara Weekes, "The potential and challenges of open data for crisis information management and aid efficiency", ICT4Peace Foundation, March 2012, <http://ict4peace.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/The-potential-and-challenges-of-open-data-for-crisis-information-management-and-aid-efficiency.pdf>

¹⁸ <http://google.org/crisismap>

¹⁹ <http://ecocrowd.wordpress.com/2010/11/22/crowdsourcing-a-new-idea-for-innovating/>

3.6 UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF CRISIS COMMUNICATIONS

As discussed in Section 5.5, poor use or performance of the technological tools described in this report could damage the credibility of responsible officials or agencies, provoke unnecessary costs or even panic (for example, in the case of a false alert), or in general lead to poor crisis management. In all cases, emerging technologies should only be used in real crises when sufficient confidence exists in their capability, and in the capability of responsible users, so that the expected benefits sufficiently outweigh the potential risks of such technology deployment. An important point with respect to the performance of emerging technologies in the area under consideration in this deliverable is that the many and advanced technologies entering play in the context of crisis management cause a significant increase in the overall technical complexity of the crisis management tools being used.

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4 EMERGING SOCIAL MEDIA APPLICATIONS

Especially in times of crisis, clear, complete and quick information is needed. ‘Disasters are threatening and highly dynamic situations, marked by high levels of information need and low levels of information availability.’²⁰ Research shows that advances in information and communication technologies enlarge the possibilities for people to seek, get and send information about their situation, feelings and capacities in critical situations. In that way, the information technology is an essential factor for streamlined search and rescue actions during disasters, but also for sufficient preparation and recovery, stimulated and organised by the authorities.

The value of social networks during and after disasters, an example

An example in which all the phases of crisis management in relation to the possibilities of information and communication become visible is presented in a scientific article with results from a study of musicians in New Orleans in the aftermath of Hurricane Katrina, August 2005.²¹ In the first hours after the beginning of the hurricane, cell phones and Internet were used for locating family, friends and other relatives. The new technologies function as an addition on traditional media like broadcast news, which didn’t supply all the information the musicians needed. As a result of the massive search to new relevant information, communities were created within social networks. People with the same interests were linked and these social networks replaced the ‘physical environments from which the musicians were barred’. For the people who had to leave the city after the hurricane, the social communities were the only manner to stay in contact with their former local communities. People who stayed have a way to share those experiences in the affected areas. Just in the recovery phase, on the moment that some musicians came back, the activity on the social networks took off. Those who returned focused on rebuilding the physical society, those who remained away found the social activities insufficient to hold a bond with their own environment.

4.1 SOCIAL NETWORKS DURING DIFFERENT PHASES OF CRISIS MANAGEMENT

As partners showed in D1.1, the process of crisis management can be subdivided in different phases. In every phase the use of social networks (as well as other communication technologies) can be of value in their own way.

4.1.1 Preparation phase

Social media can be used for making diagnoses of vulnerabilities in systems and infrastructures. Besides, some applications can facilitate the warning of citizens in the period before a threatening crisis occurs. As partners made visible in deliverable 1.2 the effects of past disasters (like wild fires and storms/floods) could have been reduced by better providing of information. Social media can be the vehicle of that information. Different forms have to be distinguished. People and groups can be connected by social networking sites like Facebook and Google+, a short message network like Twitter, (mobile) sites where photos are

²⁰ Shklovski, Ilrina, Moira Burke, Sara Kiesler and Robert Kraut, Technology adoption and use in the aftermath of Hurricane Katrina in New Orleans, *American Behavioral Scientist*, Vol. 53, Issue 8, 2010, pp. 1228-1246.

²¹ Ibid.

shared like Instagram and applications for video sharing like YouTube. For years new applications are in their developing stage (these will be examined at the end of this section).

Surveys of the American Red Cross show that a large part of the population in the United States is interested in technologies, applications or simply receiving emails for emergency communication. Information about the location of food and water, shelter locations, road closures, the location of medical services and about how to keep safe during emergencies are high rated by around a half of the questioned people. On the other hand, more than a half of the citizens who is using social media says they should post relevant information on their sites or applications during periods of crisis.²²

For example the emergency management in Plano, Texas, uses Facebook to inform citizens on a daily basis with messages that are potentially relevant to their needs. It is to make connection with the different distinguished forms of behaviour of public that is using social media, described by Hughes et al.²³ Another example of using social media during the preparation phase is the monitoring of Twitter and Facebook during the Inauguration of President Obama in 2009, considering if there was situational information that was not obtained by the more formal sources.²⁴

4.1.2 Response phase

On the one hand social media can be used to facilitate and simplify search and rescue actions. The registration of victims is fully dependent on the availability of correct and complete information. The monitoring of messages on for example Facebook and Twitter by the Red Cross has the intention to identify victims and other persons who need special aid. On the other hand emerging technologies can be useful in situations in which traditional media are not able to present the right information or voice telephony technologies are disconnected. In such moments social networks replace the tasks of the physical society. Survivors can receive the information they need and let their relatives know of their status. The following emerging technologies, contributed by Google, can improve the work and results of search and rescue teams.

- Google person finder is a web application that provides information about the status of family members, friends and other relatives affected by disasters. By entering information in this application, it will be accessible by and visible for anyone. Because people are often separated in the first hours after a disaster, it's very useful to have a technology that collects all different pieces of information. By entering the website of Google Person Finder, it displays the most current disasters. Visitors are distinguished in those who are looking for someone and those who have information about someone. The database of the application links the information and informs the people who are looking for someone when the information is available.
- Google Glass is useful to members of search and rescue teams by giving them critical and relevant information, without impeding their mission. The Google Glass will be a

²² Page, Sabrina, Karin Freberg and Kristin Saling, Emerging Media Crisis Value Model: A Comparison of Relevant, Timely Message Strategies for Emergency Events. *Journal of Strategic Security*, Vol. 6, Issue 2, 213, pp. 20-31.

²³ Hughes, A., Leysia Palen, Jeannette Sutton, Sophia Liu and Sarah Vieweg, *Site-seeing in Disaster: An Examination of On-Line Social Convergence*. ISCRAM08.

²⁴ Federal News Radio, DHS Listens and Learns from Ogma. July 25, 2009. www.federalnewsradio.com.

tool that gives the information the user needs. When a fireman enters a building, information about the characteristics of both the fire and the building can be showed on his glass. For a member of a search and rescue team it can be useful to know what the medical records of a wounded survivor are. The possibility of getting the information they need on the specific emergency situation is one of the biggest advantages of the development of the Google Glass.²⁵

- The application of Google Maps can be used during the preparation phase, to trace vulnerable areas. Furthermore, Google is able to change the maps in the application instantly, to give an updated view from affected areas. Hour by hour and day-by-day situations are changing, as we saw during hurricanes like Isaac²⁶ and Sandy²⁷ (both in 2012). That has huge implications for search and rescue teams and other actors involved in the process. To them updated information about the affected area is very important. In the updated version of Google Maps public alerts, active shelters, YouTube videos and recent maps of before the crisis can be viewed.

Figure 4: Example of map from the Google person finder²⁸

4.1.3 Recovery phase

The value of social media and mobile technology lies in the fact that people have more control over the situation (when those technologies are used in the preparation phase) and that

²⁵ David, K., *3 Ways Google Will Transform Government*. August 29, 2013.

<http://www.govloop.com/profiles/blogs/3-ways-google-glass-will-transform-government>

²⁶ <http://google.org/crisismap/2012-tropical-system-isaac>

²⁷ <http://google.org/crisismap/2012-sandy>

²⁸ <http://www.inhabitat.com/wp-content/uploads/2010/03/googlefinder-ed01.jpg>

they have more connection with and control over the community.²⁹ Or: ‘social media combine the use of innovative strategies with digital communication technology platforms, enabling the user to share knowledge, engage in digital storytelling through conversations and visual components, and collaborate with others.’³⁰ Research by the University of San Francisco’s Masters of Public Administration department shows the high activity on social networks during disasters. Research among survivors of social media shows that 25% of them downloaded disaster-related apps, 20% have used an emergency app, 35% directly post a request for help on a responder’s Facebook page and 76% contact friends for telling that they are safe.³¹ In general (not only the victims or survivors), not less than 80% of the Americans expect emergency response agencies to monitor the stream of messages on social media and respond to the senders of those messages. Although the American figures won’t be the same as in Europe, western societies are nevertheless comparable.

Not only the general activity and findings are showed, also the social media use during particular disasters has been examined. Some examples, which show the usefulness during the preparation, response and recovery phases:

- 1) During the tornado season in the United States, social media have been used to generate ideas for the rebuilding of cities. In Tuscaloosa, a social media website was created for sharing ideas between residents. 300 ideas were generated and shared on their Facebook pages by over 4,000 visitors.
- 2) On the first day after the Japan tsunami, Facebook recorded 4,5 million status updates from around the world, with the keywords ‘Japan’, ‘Tsunami’ or ‘Earthquake’. That was 84% of all worldwide status updates on the 11th of March 2011.
- 3) In the period between January 12 and January 14 2010, the first days after the devastating earthquake in Haiti, 2.3 million tweets were composed with the key words ‘Haiti’ or ‘Red Cross’. Almost 10% of those tweets contained the number ‘90999’, which meant a donation of 10 dollars for the Red Cross.
- 4) In the first aftermath of hurricane Sandy the top 5 of most shared terms on Facebook exists out of ‘we are ok’, ‘power’, ‘damage’, ‘hope everyone is ok’ and ‘trees’. FEMA tweeted to its followers on Twitter that phone services probably were out of service and that send texts or updating social networks were the best ways to inform loved ones that you were OK.

According to the Washington Post³², during the Boston bombings, March 2013, millions of people used Facebook as a place for on one hand getting information and on the other hand sympathise with victims and their relatives. In this way, social media and social networks are like the market places of ancient times, with the huge amount of present people as the most important difference. The casual business that social media usually are, changes in times of

²⁹ Shklovski, Burke, Kieslerb and Kraut, 2010, pp. 1228-1246.

³⁰ Page, Sabrina, Karen Freberg and Kristin Saling, Emerging Media Crisis Value Model: A Comparison of Relevant Timely Message Strategies for Emergency Events. *Journal of Strategic Security*, Vol. 6, Issue 2, 2013, pp. 20-31.

³¹ Scott, 2013, http://socialtimes.com/even-the-red-cross-uses-social-media-during-natural-disasters-infographic_b132228

³² Petri, Alexandra, The explosions at the Boston Marathon and the Facebook Huddle, *The Washington Post*, April 15 2013. <http://www.washingtonpost.com/blogs/compost/wp/2013/04/15/the-explosions-at-the-boston-marathon-and-the-facebook-huddle/>

crisis in a way to contact the most important people in your life, as well as a way to gather the most relevant and important information. ‘It’s a strange new ritual – the frantic phone call from Mom, multiplied and stretched over a thousand fainter connections.’³³ With that knowledge it appears that the benefits of social media for authorities during crisis situations have to be stressed too.

Although Twitter is already a longer existing medium, it’s one of the most used social media devices in the world. ‘A wide range of studies suggest that information sharing networks, such as twitter, can be very useful in times of crisis by quickly and effectively disseminating relevant news.’³⁴ Research on the possible benefits of Twitter for people involved in the earthquake and tsunami in Japan, March 2011, shows that rescue teams saved people who send tweets about their critical situations. People who posted messages to let their followers know that they were safe or unharmed were mobilised to help during the rescue actions. However, the high number of unreliable retweets is one of the weak characteristics of this medium. Some of the solutions offered by the respondents, and subscribed by the research team, is to introduce official hash tags (in particular for cases of emergency) and to limit the possible number of retweets with such a hash tag. Also allowing users to trace information but remain anonymous is one of the options to cope with the emerging problems of Twitter during crisis situations and disasters.

4.2 GENERAL DEVELOPMENTS IN TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS

Besides the development of new applications, which will be presented later in this project, an important development in the world of social media is the structural screening of social media messages by large companies. They are building NASA style “mission control centres”, for monitoring and responding to the massive stream of tweets on Twitter and messages on Facebook and other applications, regarding their company.³⁵ While public authorities are not companies and the importance of tweets and other messages for multinationals is quite different than for public services in times of disasters, the idea of monitoring processes on social media is the same. Whereas 80% of the executives of companies believe that their market and profits can grow by monitoring and using social media³⁶, the real activity of local and regional authorities on one hand and emergency organisations on the other hand on platforms as Twitter and Facebook is relatively limited, and the benefits of such an approach are still not recognised enough.

However, a very energetic actor in social media is the international Red Cross and that is why they opened, March 2012, a Digital Operations Centre.³⁷ The aim of this initiative of the Red Cross is to reach out and respond to victims during natural disasters such as hurricanes, wild fires and earthquakes. Both media coverage and posts of family members who are seeking for their relatives are monitored and reacted to. An example of a disaster during which this

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Acar, Adam. and Yuya Muraki. Twitter for Crisis Communication: Lessons Learnt from Japan’s Tsunami Disaster. *International Journal of Web based Communities*. Vol. 7, Issue 3, 2011, pp. 392-402.

³⁵ Holmes, Ryan, NASA-style mission centers for social media are taking off. *Fortune*. October 25, 2012. <http://tech.fortune.cnn.com/2012/10/25/nasa-style-mission-control-centers-for-social-media-are-taking-off/>

³⁶ Feldman, Bob, Michael Gale, Jeff Hunt and Paul Walker, *The Economics of the Socially Engaged Enterprise*, PulsePoint Group, 2012.

³⁷ Hoover, J. Nicholas, Inside Red Cross Social Media Command Center, *Information Week*, March 20, 2012. <http://www.informationweek.com/government/information-management/inside-red-cross-social-media-command-ce/232602698?pgno=1#slideshowPageTop>

monitoring was very successful, was hurricane Sandy. 23 employees of the Red Cross monitored 2.5 million social media postings, related to the hurricane. 4,500 of those messages were followed up with aid for people in need.³⁸ Also the usage of social media among authorities and public leaders is growing. 77% of all the world leaders are active on Twitter.³⁹ Not only individuals, also organisations increasingly take a role within social networks. For example the government of the United States uses social media for communications to assist during day-to-day emergency operations.⁴⁰ The value of activity is underlined by the following statement: ‘the more that the needs of the public are considered, the more they can be active participants in preparation for, response to and recovery from emergencies.’⁴¹

Companies as examples for authorities during disasters

Sometimes, companies can be good examples for public authorities. That seems to be the fact with the Dutch airline company KLM. All different divisions of the enterprise are united in a Customer Care department.⁴² Most important cause for this strategy was the volcano eruption in Iceland, in 2010, a disaster that halted aviation in much of Europe for many days. Initially, KLM placed update messages on the official website, but due to the enormous attention of interest people, the site went offline. Afterwards, Twitter and Facebook became the most important vehicles of both receiving and sending information. Almost all questions to the account @klm were answered within some hours⁴³ and with the current 24/7 capacity load all questions will be answered within one hour. The example shows that the quality of crisis communication during the different phases of a disaster is determined by factors as quickness and fairness. Both providing information and giving citizens a perspective of action are very relevant during crises.

Interviews with people with expertise in marketing, social media and other emerging technologies indicate two other general developments in the world of social media/networks:

- Tablets and mobile phones gain more and more ground compared to personal computers. Increasingly, new technologies will only be visible and accessible by mobile devices. That has complications for the design of content and layout.
- Because disasters and crisis can destroy or disconnect mobile services, developers of applications try to make more applications accessible in an offline status. Examples of these are apps with information about what to do during emergency situations.

4.3 CONDITIONS FOR USEFUL TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS

³⁸ Scott, Cameron, Even the Red Cross Uses Social Media During Natural Disasters: Infographic, *Social Times, Your Social Media Source*, July 17 2013. http://socialtimes.com/even-the-red-cross-uses-social-media-during-natural-disasters-infographic_b132228

³⁹ Twiplomacy, *The Best connected World Leaders on Twitter*, 2013. <http://twiplomacy.com>

⁴⁰ Collins, H., Emergency Managers and First Responders Use Twitter and Facebook to Update Communities, *Emergency Management Magazine*, July 27, 2009

⁴¹ White, Connie and Linda Plotnick, A Framework to Identify Best Practices: Social Media and Web 2.0 Technologies in the Emergency Domain, *International Journal of Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 1, 2010, pp.

⁴² Oosterveer, Danny. *KLM 24 uur per dag te bereiken via sociale media.*, Marketingfacts. 25 juli 2011. http://www.marketingfacts.nl/berichten/20110722_klm_24_uur_per_dag_te_bereiken_via_sociale_media

⁴³ Van der Velden, Nick, *KLM twittert er op los: Waar is Schiphol?*, Marketingfacts. 19 april 2010. http://www.marketingfacts.nl/berichten/20100419_klm_twittert_er_op_los._waar_is_schiphol

Communication in a crisis period needs three elements: openness, fairness and quickness.⁴⁴ We can see again these factors in the Emerging Media Crisis Value Model⁴⁵. This is a model that describes important factors of communication during crisis situations, combined with measurement scales to categorise the performance of chosen systems based on stakeholders' values. Stakeholders can for example be the local authorities, members of search and rescue teams or citizens. By using the emerging media crisis value model research can link different methods of communication with scores on the different sub-functions. Below the general function of crisis communication (sending and receiving information during crises or disasters) a crisis message has some sub-functions too:

Figure 5: Essentials for crisis communication

Some sub-functions apply more or less on several disasters. Showing credibility is about taking responsibility for a crisis that will be less the case during a natural disaster as a hurricane, although responsibility can be taken for an insufficient preparation phase. Different emerging technologies and applications can be tested on the sub-functions, presented above. For instance, if an emerging technology has a small time of first response and can be used for complete messages, but reaches only a small number of citizens, the actors involved have to make choices about which measures have to be used for which crisis communication message.

Partners spoke with some experts in the field of social media and marketing and distinguish the following upcoming social media and social networks for the next couple of years. First we describe the application or technology, next we summarise the way in which the social network can be an advantage for the use in crisis situations.

- **Medium:** a blogging site, created by the founders of Twitter and Blogger, Evan Williams and Biz Stone. People can write a blog about several subjects, and the amount of votes of users (as Likes on Facebook) determines how prominent the blog is displayed on the page. Furthermore, like LinkedIn, it's a social network that only allows invited members to see messages.

How it can be used during crisis situations: Medium can be seen as an instrument to connect people. One of the main problems of already existing social media like

⁴⁴ Jong, W., M. Petit and J. Jochmann. Overheidscommunicatie als instrument. In: I. Helsloot & J.V. Steenbergen, *Infectieziektebestrijding: Studies naar organisatie en praktijkwerking*. BJu. 2005.

⁴⁵ Freberg, Karen, Kristen Saling, Kathleen Vidoloff and Gina Eosco, *What makes a good social media crisis message?: Challenging traditional methodology through qualitative and quantitative value modeling*. Paper presented at the 16th International Conference on Corporate Reputation, Brand, Identity and Competitiveness, Milan, Italy, 2012.

Twitter and Facebook is the noise of information and the fact that it is often not clear if information is sent by official senders or by others, like citizens. It undermines the credibility of the message. When citizens in a defined area or with specific characteristics become member of a page on medium, authorities know exactly if a message will reach their target group. The importance of a message will be showed by the prominence of the place where it is showed.

- Conversations: a social network for companies, a sort of Facebook into the workplace. Members of different teams and in the future employees of different companies can communicate by short posts on message style, instead of by long email chains. It can be seen as a digital notice board.

How it can be used during crisis situations: One of the most critical points in crisis situations is the tuning between different actors involved. Communication is lacking or fails. With a simply accessible social network, like conversations, people can react on each other with short and ‘to the point’ notices. When also public organisations use this application, it can create a network of the key actors before and during crisis situations.

- Whisper: an app for the iPhone, which can be used to post secret messages. Members of the application can read the posts, respond with another whisper or send messages to the anonymous sender.

How it can be used during crisis situations: Whisper can be used to enlarge awareness about possible threats and vulnerabilities. Whistle-blowers get a platform to attend the authorities on maltreatments. In fact, the disadvantage of such an application is the lack of control on the identity of senders and so on the credibility of the information.

Figure 6: Whisper app logo⁴⁶

Some other emerging social networks won't be useful and effective for use in the period before or during a disaster. For example Pheed, a ‘pay-as-you-go social network’ where people have to pay a monthly fee for access to photos, videos and texts. Considering the important aspect of ‘broad communication’, Pheed doesn't seem to be an emerging social network with big implications for the future. Also deviantArt, a social network site for artists and art enthusiasts, and because of the target group (80% of the users are 18 to 29 years old) an interesting social medium for the future, won't be effective in crisis situations.

⁴⁶ <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/whisper-share-express-meet/id506141837>

5 RELATED EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATION AREAS

In this section we analyse each of the 27 emerging technology and application areas identified in Table 1 of section 2 with regard to their background and their potential use in crisis management in combination with the services of social media.

5.1 CITIZEN JOURNALISM

The appearance of citizen journalism is significant because journalism has long been an overwhelmingly professional activity. “Freedom of the press is guaranteed only to those who own one”⁴⁷, but now billions of people own technology enabling global publication of the media they produce – thus, everybody can fulfil the role of a journalist (but does not necessarily do so).

Journalism is often an important factor in crisis situations. The decisions that a society will make in response to a crisis depend on the available information, which is now often heavily influenced by citizen journalism⁴⁸. Such decisions for example include providing aid money to people in need, or applying political pressure to government organisations to adapt their behaviour (for example⁴⁹, the U.S. air force in the aftermath of the 2010 Haiti earthquake denied clearance to land to an airplane carrying vital aid from Doctors Without Borders, until Twitter was used to raise the problem in the public domain).

In the context of citizen journalism, we can study the role of social media in allowing everybody to contribute to the public knowledge of matters of public concern, and in the context of crisis management, we can study how the ensuing new forms of information flow influence a society’s reaction to crisis situations.

5.1.1 Background

The term citizen journalism is used to refer to “the involvement of non-professionals in reporting news, especially in blogs and other websites”⁵⁰. A politically charged, insightful definition is: “When the people formerly known as the audience employ the press tools they have in their possession to inform one another”⁵¹. Citizen journalism arises out of a conceptually simple but extremely powerful capability offered by new communication technologies, and especially social media, to every user of such technology: the capability to broadcast information. The information being broadcast must be “news”, i.e. address factual, ongoing events of public concern, and inform society about itself, potentially making public events that would otherwise remain private⁵². It sometimes occurs, though these are incidental and not necessary features of citizen journalism, that the reporting is a conscious choice of the

⁴⁷ A. J. Liebling, in "Do you belong in journalism?", *The New Yorker* (14 May 1960)

⁴⁸ As, for example, is discussed in the Case Studies of deliverable D2.2 of the COSMIC project

⁴⁹ COSMIC D2.2

⁵⁰ Citizen journalism. (n.d.). *Collins English Dictionary - Complete & Unabridged 10th Edition*. Retrieved September 20, 2013

⁵¹ Jay Rosen (14). "A Most Useful Definition of Citizen Journalism". *PressThink*.

⁵² Harcup, Tony (2009), “Journalism: Principles and Practice”, Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications, ISBN 978-1847872500

reporter to inform the public, that citizen journalism is conducted in close collaboration with professional journalism, and that citizen journalism is a collaborative activity⁵³.

Because it is able to provide the public with news that professional journalism may fail to offer, as discussed above, citizen journalism is very important for crisis management. Interestingly, crisis management is also important for citizen journalism. It is in the context of crisis management that citizen journalism is considered to have begun⁵⁴, and it is a context in which it has great influence: in a time of widespread confusion and events unfolding too quickly for a few individuals to collect and curate the relevant information, the decentralised, real-time, large-scale capabilities of citizen journalism become significant advantages⁵⁵.

Figure 7: Citizen Journalism – Billboard⁵⁶

5.1.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Citizen journalism is an “application area” rather than a “technology area”. That is, it involves new capabilities, and new behaviours, enabled and engendered by new technology. Therefore, it does not have an immediate technical impact on crisis management. However, being a critically important application area, it is one of the factors that make social media critically important technological tools during crises.

5.2 CLOUD

Cloud computing is a modern paradigm of distributed computing used to provide content and services over the network (predominantly the internet) – it transforms computing into a utility, as it allows service providers to (relatively easily) deploy whatever infrastructure is necessary in order for them to provide the desired services to users⁵⁷. (However, the term cloud

⁵³ David Cohn, “Time citizen journalism pulled its acts together”, 15 November 2007, PressGazette, <http://www.pressgazette.co.uk/node/39443>

⁵⁴ Allen, Stuart, and Einar Thorsen, eds. *Citizen journalism: Global perspectives*. Vol. 1. Peter Lang, 2009.

⁵⁵ see, for example: “The Haitian News Vacuum”, *Columbia Journalism Review*, 13 January 2010

⁵⁶ <http://pressinamerica.pbworks.com/w/page/18360163/Citizen%20Journalism>

⁵⁷ Armbrust, Michael, et al. “A view of cloud computing.” *Communications of the ACM* 53.4 (2010): 50-58.

computing does not have a commonly agreed scientific definition, and, rather, reflects a general understanding of multiple technologies used according to a practically important paradigm⁵⁸).

5.2.1 Background

A variety of underlying technologies create the cloud, most prominently distributed computing and virtualisation; key technical features of the cloud's infrastructure are multi-tenancy (resource pooling), massive scalability (on-demand self-service), rapid elasticity (automatic increase or decrease of resources committed to providing a service), and measured service (pay-per-use)⁵⁹.

Most social media can be considered to be cloud services. Many communication technologies that have been provided specifically for crisis management related communications can also be considered to be cloud services. Examples include: Facebook⁶⁰ and Twitter, Ushahidi⁶¹ and Google Crisis Maps⁶².

5.2.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Cloud computing provides vast resources for a vast range of existing technical solutions that are, or new ones that could be, employed to manage a crisis. For example, data mining, decision support, pattern recognition and event prediction, natural language processing⁶³ and many more technologies can use cloud resources to access the necessary computing resources, or can be based on the cloud so that any user, regardless of location and available hardware, can access them provided only that web access is available.

Cloud computing also facilitates the combination of services provided by different actors. For example, one provider may offer storage for vast amounts of crowdsourced data, while a different provider may offer powerful statistical or machine intelligence tools to process this data⁶⁴ – the combination allowing users to both access and understand comprehensive data about a crisis.

5.3 CROWDSOURCING

Volunteers have long been an important force in crisis management. Crowdsourcing is a practice of distributing work to a “crowd” of contributors, thus managing to perform larger amounts of work than may otherwise be possible. Social networks facilitate the organisation

⁵⁸ http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Cloud_computing&oldid=573703556

⁵⁹ Carlin, Sean, and Kevin Curran. "Cloud Computing Technologies." *International Journal of Cloud Computing and Services Science (IJ-CLOSER)* 1.2 (2012): 59-65.

⁶⁰ Lenk, Alexander, et al. "What's inside the Cloud? An architectural map of the Cloud landscape." *Proceedings of the 2009 ICSE Workshop on Software Engineering Challenges of Cloud Computing*. IEEE Computer Society, 2009.

⁶¹ Morrow, Nathan, et al. "Independent evaluation of the Ushahidi Haiti project." *Development Information Systems International* 8 (2011)

⁶² "The Google Crisis Maps: Superstorm Sandy – excellent online resources post-Hurricane Sandy", 11/05/12, <http://queens.brownstoner.com/tag/fuel/>

⁶³ these examples are all discussed in this document

⁶⁴ Noordhuis, Pieter, Michiel Heijkoop, and Alexander Lazovik. "Mining twitter in the cloud: A case study." *Cloud Computing (CLOUD), 2010 IEEE 3rd International Conference on*. IEEE, 2010.

However, tools exist to facilitate crowdsourcing, e.g. mapping platforms⁷¹, tools for information sharing⁷², and tools for finding workers⁷³. Crises are often sudden and unexpected, therefore it is important that organisational resources are already available and ready to be used when a crisis strikes. Crowdsourcing is particularly effective at collecting information that is not centrally available, but where many individuals can each contribute a small amount of valuable data.

5.4 DATA MINING AND BIG DATA

Social media are a valuable communication tool that can be used to manage crises – for example, authorities can post warnings or instructions to people threatened by or undergoing a crisis; survivors can stay in contact with family and loved ones, reporting on their situation, or receiving psychological support; or political pressure can be put on governments, through the immediate dissemination of important news, to prioritise humanitarian action over exploiting a crisis so as to follow a questionable political agenda. In many useful applications, people communicate directly with other people – writing, reading, posting photos, and so on.

However, people also risk being inundated with vast amounts of information – what can an aid agency do if thousands, or even millions, of people begin to tweet about an ongoing disaster?

Figure 9: Two Big Data visualisations^{74,75}

Also, vast amounts of information are available, and can be useful in managing a crisis, which were not originally intended for all of the valuable uses to which they can be put – for example, when individual users mention the symptoms of an illness they are experiencing to their loved ones, they may do this with the intention of communicating their family and loved ones, but a survey of all such social posts can be invaluable for an epidemiological analysis. However, how can an analyst process the vast amounts of data involved in such communication? Especially when analysing social content without prior knowledge of what conclusion is expected, huge amounts of data must be checked against huge numbers of possible threats. For example, in an after-the-event study of social media posts to determine

⁷¹ such as opendatakit.org and ncg.nuim.ie/i2maps

⁷² www.ushahidi.com

⁷³ www.mturk.com

⁷⁴ <http://wikibon.org/blog/hadoop-big-data-focus-shifting-to-analytics-and-visualization/>

⁷⁵ <http://silvertontconsulting.com/blog/2011/06/24/big-data-part-3/>

whether the outbreak of an epidemic could have been detected early by analysing these posts, a relatively small amount of social media content may suffice for the analysis; however, in an ongoing process of constantly monitoring social media in order to detect any valuable epidemiological insights, a much larger proportion of social media content must be analysed, and much more complex analysis is required in order to enable the possibility of detecting unknown public health threats.

Big data is the technological paradigm that enables such useful analysis of such vast quantities of data to be achieved in practice.

5.4.1 Background

According to IBM in 2012, “everyday, we create 2.5 quintillion bytes of data”⁷⁶. Social media contribute huge amounts of data to this total, for example, on average: 400 million Tweets are tweeted every day⁷⁷, 30 billion pieces of content are shared each month on Facebook⁷⁸, 100 hours of video are uploaded to YouTube every minute⁷⁹, 55 million photos are uploaded to Instagram daily⁸⁰.

Big data is the collection of scientific and engineering methods and tools for dealing with such volumes of data, and addresses not merely the storage but also access to and distribution, analysis, and useful presentation of results (such as visualisation of analysis of the data) for huge volumes of data^{81,82,83}. It exploits a multitude of scientific disciplines including high performance and distributed computing, visualisation, data mining, statistics, and machine intelligence.

5.4.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Big data is a very important technological area. It is a major challenge to deal with the vast amounts of data described above, and to perform the complicated analyses of this data that is required in order to draw useful conclusions.

Big data is not a particular kind of analysis. It is not intended to enable only a specific category of conclusions to be drawn. Rather, it is the overall field of data science that addresses usefully exploiting large amounts of data. Therefore, it provides a technical foundation for any kind of collection and analysis of social media content for crisis management, ranging from epidemiological analysis, through assessing the severity of early reports of the damage caused by extreme weather conditions, to tracking social unrest in the

⁷⁶ <http://www-01.ibm.com/software/au/data/bigdata>

⁷⁷ <https://business.twitter.com/whos-twitter>, on 17/09/2013

⁷⁸ <http://blog.kissmetrics.com/facebook-statistics/?wide=1>, on 17/09/2013

⁷⁹ <http://www.youtube.com/yt/press/statistics.html>, on 17/09/2013

⁸⁰ <http://instagram.com/press>, on 17/09/2013

⁸¹ LaValle, Steve, et al. "Big data, analytics and the path from insights to value." *MIT Sloan Management Review* 52.2 (2011): 21-31.

⁸² Kusnetzky, Dan, "What is "Big Data?", 16/2/2010, ZDNet, <http://www.zdnet.com/blog/virtualization/what-is-big-data/1708>

⁸³ Vance, Ashley, "Start-Up Goes After Big Data With Hadoop Helper", New York Times Blog, 22 April 2010, <http://bits.blogs.nytimes.com/2010/04/22/start-up-goes-after-big-data-with-hadoop-helper>

wake of the undemocratic behaviour of governments such as often occurs throughout the world, e.g. in Africa⁸⁴, Asia⁸⁵, Europe⁸⁶ or America⁸⁷.

Big data is becoming a critical part of crisis communication due to our expanding view of the very definition of what comprises communication. Crisis communication does not involve only intentional, explicit exchange of messages – such as first responders talking over a voice connection, or a broadcast of a text message warning to citizens threatened by an approaching natural disaster. Rather, crisis communication also involves the monitoring and understanding of the full body of public, openly available communication – such as messages and content being publicly exchanged on social media. Thus, individuals may be reporting their condition to loved ones or making specific requests for help, but a complete analysis of all communications can reveal valuable information of general scope, such as a disease outbreak⁸⁸, as discussed above.

5.5 DECISION SUPPORT

As framed in more precision in the following sub-section, Decision Support Systems can improve decision making in difficult circumstances, under uncertainty, risk, hard-to-define objectives (e.g. when facing moral or operational dilemmas as to which outcomes may be preferable) and rapidly changing conditions.

Therefore, their application to crisis management is highly promising, as crisis conditions match their expected operating environment:

During a crisis, neither human experts nor technological tools can be guaranteed to perform perfectly – not just final outcomes, but also intermediate steps of analysis, communication and intervention will be have fluid and unpredictable results.

Decision Support Systems provide a technological background, but also a body of best practices, for including scientific tools (such as weather forecasting), as well as more human considerations, in an integrated system for responding to crises. Critically, the human considerations include managing communications: dealing with credibility, panic, indifference, speed and reach issues of crisis communication.

5.5.1 Background

⁸⁴ Jack Shenker, “Fighting between police and protesters is worst since Mubarak's fall as new leaders accused of same slow tactics on reform”, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2011/jun/29/cairo-street-clashes-demonstrators-police-egypt>

⁸⁵ “Chinese Communist party officials on trial accused of torturing man to death”, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/sep/17/chinese-communist-party-trial-torture>

⁸⁶ Aris Chatzistefanou, “Officer says government has turned blind eye to fascists and far right may be being used to provoke clashes with demonstrators”, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2012/oct/26/golden-dawn-infiltrated-greek-police-claims>

⁸⁷ Glenn Greenwald and Ewen MacAskill, “NSA Prism program taps in to user data of Apple, Google and others”, <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/jun/06/us-tech-giants-nsa-data>

⁸⁸ Hirschfeld, D. Twitter data accurately tracked Haiti cholera outbreak. Available from <http://www.nature.com/news/twitter-data-accurately-tracked-haiti-choleraoutbreak-1.9770>.

Decision Support Systems address human, expert, decision making, aiming to improve it by providing useful data and analysis⁸⁹. In other words, the Decision Support System helps the expert in the decision making process, rather than replacing the expert by making decisions for her/him. Decision Support Systems normally address “soft” problems that are not completely technically specified and whose solution requires human intuition – providing the human expert with as much hard data, analysis and visualisation as possible in order to improve the decision making process – explicitly taking into account the subjectivity of the decision to be made, acknowledging the necessity to take a decision based on incomplete data, or facilitating the exploration of a problem not fully understood. Decision Support Systems are usually tools for users who are not expert computer users, or computer scientists, thus their usability is a key feature. They aim to be adaptable to changing situations and the different intuitive preferences of their users. Overall, dealing with uncertainty is a key element in Decision Support Systems, which can be defined as follows: “computer based systems that help decision-makers confront ill-structured problems through direct interaction with data and analysis models”⁹⁰.

Both during the design and implementation of Decision Support Systems, and when using them in action, we address the full spectrum of real concerns that a practical environment entails.

5.5.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Decision Support Systems in crisis management address scenario formulation, risk assessment, risk management, and communication⁹¹. Communication represents an integrating factor between the processes of understanding the situation, taking action, and involving stakeholders. A Decision Support System can contribute to the organisation and management of a large-scale communication effort, such as that conducted by a government or aid agency in response to a crisis threatening or affecting a large population. For example, human experts managing an early warning system must take into account not only the probability of a threat such as flooding, earthquakes, or hurricanes materialising, but also the potential damage that might be caused if a threat does materialise, and additionally the adverse effects of issuing a warning that proves to have been unnecessary – such as the cost of an unnecessary evacuation, loss of confidence in the early warning system itself. Thus, managing communication to the public is just as challenging a decision process for officials as the scientific estimation of an actual threat’s significance and likelihood^{92, 93}.

⁸⁹ Sprague, R. H., Jr., "A Framework for the Development of Decision Support Systems," *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, vol. 4, no. 4, Dec. 1980, pp. 1-26.

⁹⁰ McNurlin, B. C., & Sprague, R. H. (2004). *Information systems management in practice* (6th ed.) Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

⁹¹ Prelipcean, Gabriela, and Mircea Boscoianu. "Emerging Applications of Decision Support Systems (DSS) in Crisis Management." *Efficient Decision Support Systems—Practice and Challenges in Multidisciplinary Domains*, Prof. Chiang Jao (Ed.), InTech (2011).

⁹² Grasso, Veronica F., and Ashbindu Singh. "Early warning systems: State-of-art analysis and future directions." *United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)*, 2012.

⁹³ Rogers, David, and Vladimir Tsirkunov. "Costs and Benefits of Early Warning Systems." *Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction, 16pp., Published by ISDR and World Bank* (2011).

Figure 10: “Decision support system developed for effective disaster safety response”⁹⁴

5.6 6. E-INCLUSION AND E-ACCOUNTABILITY

The introduction of every new technology leads to a distinction between people who are more easily able to acquire this technology, and people that have difficulties to obtain this new technology. In contemporary society nearly everyone owns a computer, tablet or mobile phone (IT-tool) that enables easy access to new media and to information on the Internet or to share personal information. However there are still people in Europe who are excluded from the benefits of the current informational society, since they have no access to internet and subsequently can't use new media. It is for this reason that e-inclusion is often seen in the context of social justice (and awareness) in Europe.⁹⁵ Moreover people who have access and who are capable to publish information, which they like, can easily harm other people on social media.

5.6.1 Background

The term ‘e-inclusion’ refers to “*the conception that all citizens should have access to ICTs and should be able to make effective use of them.*”⁹⁶ The 2005 Community Survey on ICT shows that more than one third of European citizens do not have access to a computer and 37% of these citizens between the ages of 16-74 lack basic computer skills.⁹⁷ There is a relationship between poverty and social or e-exclusion, however other socio-demographic factors must be taken into account for the digital divide between those who effectively can use new media and those who can't. Various surveys revealed that geography, income, social status, gender, age and disabilities are related to e-inclusion.⁹⁸ The highest scores of e-inclusion are found in Northern Europe (Scandinavia) and the lowest scores in Southern Europe.⁹⁹ While ICT on the one hand promises greater access to information and connectivity

⁹⁴ http://www.narlabs.org.tw/en/news/news.php?news_id=512

⁹⁵ Macinelli, E. (2007). “E-Inclusion in the Information Society”. Budapest: Leonardo da Vinci & Netis; Hollier, S. & Murray, I (2006). “The evolution of E-inclusion: Technology in Education for the Vision-impaired.” Western Australian: Cornell University ILR school.

⁹⁶ Macinelli, E. (2007). “e-Inclusion in the Information Society”. Budapest: Leonardo da Vinci & Netis.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Ahmed, N. (2006). “An overview of E-participation Models”. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs.

⁹⁹ Macinelli, E. (2007). “E-Inclusion in the Information Society”. Budapest: Leonardo da Vinci & Netis.

between crisis managers or emergency services and citizens, the proliferation of new technologies is also increasing rather than reducing inequalities between individuals and groups in society.¹⁰⁰ The EU member states have launched the concept of ‘e-inclusion’ in their strategy to fight social exclusion at the European Council in Nice in 2000. Based on the definition of the eEurope Advisory Group, ‘e-inclusion’ is not limited to the realisation of the preconditions for e-inclusion, such as access to ICT tools, networks and citizen literacy, because e-inclusion deals with the empowerment of people to participate in the issues they are interested in.¹⁰¹ There has emerged a lot of policy initiatives and projects to tackle the challenge of the digital divide.¹⁰² One example of such a project is Hyperstories. Hyperstories enables Chilean blind children, who are excluded from normal computer usage, to work with an IT application that incorporates sound-based software. The IT application brings a very important change to their lives, because they learn how their environment is structured which in turn can be used in daily life.¹⁰³ Other projects are also focused on specific target groups in developing countries who experience digital exclusion as a real barrier in their daily lives (such groups are young people; elderly people; women; people with disabilities).¹⁰⁴

5.6.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Crisis managers should take into account that they are responsible for the way they have informed citizens during a crisis period. Crisis managers and municipalities are able to develop a dialogue on social media or elsewhere on Internet. It is easily possible for citizens to confirm, alter or even to distribute false information. There is less control on the content of information than when citizens are informed about the crisis by traditional media (e.g. a press release).¹⁰⁵ This implies that it is important that public authorities in the field of crisis management or other first responders realise that they are responsible for the information that they have released on new media. They have to account on new media for the publishing information to afflicted people or to provide transparency in their acts.

Overall, this is not a technology area as such, but a best practice area, where crisis managers should be aware of their responsibility towards the social fabric and the of possibilities that the gap of e-inclusion may prevent social media messages reaching everybody during a crisis.

5.7 EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS

The expression ‘early warning’ is used in many fields to illustrate the provision of information on emerging dangerous circumstances where that information enables action in advance to reduce involved risks. Early warning systems forecast natural geographical and biological hazards, complex socio-political emergencies, industrial hazards, personal health risks and many other related risks.¹⁰⁶ Early warning systems can be set up to avoid or reduce the impact of hazards as floods, flashfloods, landslides, storms and forest fires. The

¹⁰⁰ Ahmed, N. (2006). “An overview of E-participation Models”. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Molina, A. (2003). “The Digital Divide: The need for a Global e-Inclusion Movement”. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*. 15(1), pp. 137-152.

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Macinelli, E. (2007). “E-Inclusion in the Information Society”. Budapest: Leonardo da Vinci & Netis.

¹⁰⁵ Uitz, S. & Schultz, F. (2012). “Is een crisis via sociale media te beheersen?” In: Kok., D. (Ed.) *Sociaal kapitaal. De meerwaarde van sociale media voor gemeenten*. Delft: Eburon.

¹⁰⁶ “Global early warning systems for natural hazards: systematic and people-centred”, Reid Basher, 2006
<http://www.unisdr.org/2006/ppew/info-resources/docs/RSTA20061819p.pdf>

significance of an effective early warning system lies in the recognition of its benefits by the members of the general public.¹⁰⁷

5.7.1 Background

Over the years, disasters have ruined lives and civilisations by killing people and damaging homes and businesses. In the past 35 years such disasters have resulted in losses estimated at 2.5 million lives and more than US\$1.5 billion, mainly in developing countries. Efforts to reduce disaster risk have therefore focused on developing early warning systems to provide timely and effective information to enable people and communities to respond when a disaster occurs.¹⁰⁸ Several countries have significantly reduced deaths by developing effective early warning systems. It is claimed that Cuba's Tropical Cyclone Early Warning System is responsible for the dramatic reduction of deaths related to weather hazards such as tropical cyclones, storm surges and floods: five successive flooding events left only seven dead.¹⁰⁹ Another example is Bangladesh, which now has a 48-hour early warning system in place that allows people to evacuate the territory and move to safe shelters hours before cyclones make landfall. In 1970, 300,000 people died as a result of Cyclone Bhola, compared to 3,000 in 2007 during Cyclone Sidr, where authorities were able to track it.¹¹⁰

5.7.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Social media may operate as an early warning system which assists crisis management especially at the response phase. As they announce valuable information, they are capable of alerting not only the public but also an organisation to an emerging problem.¹¹¹

Early warning announcements are of vital importance when it comes to a forthcoming disaster. The quick spread of alerts can provide the public with time to prepare and information about efficient ways to respond. In the case of tsunamis in Tohoku, Japan, the warnings were more coordinated than in those of the devastating Indian Ocean Tsunami in 2004, providing many people with time to evacuate to high ground.¹¹² Since earthquakes can often lead to the formation of tsunamis in Southeast Asia, announcements related to quakes and their activity can supply residents with the necessary time for an evacuation. Indonesian government agencies have transformed Twitter into a means of public information of weather-related emergencies.¹¹³

5.8 EPIDEMIOLOGY AND PREDICTION

¹⁰⁷“Early Warning System” ,<http://practicalaction.org/using-v2r-in-nepal>

¹⁰⁸“Early warning of disasters facts and figures”, Lucy Pearson

<http://www.scidev.net/global/communication/feature/early-warning-of-disasters-facts-and-figures-1.html>

¹⁰⁹Rogers, D. and V. Tsirkunov. “Costs and Benefits of Early Warning Systems “ (Paper for UNISDR, 2011)

¹¹⁰“Early warning of disasters facts and figures”, Lucy Pearson

<http://www.scidev.net/global/communication/feature/early-warning-of-disasters-facts-and-figures-1.html>

¹¹¹ Julie Ogilvie, “Social Media: Creating an Early Warning System”, December 02, 2013,

<https://www.siriusdecisions.com/Blog/2013/Dec/Social-Media-Creating-an-Early-Warning-System.aspx>

¹¹² Lucy Pearson, “Early warning of disasters facts and figures”,

<http://www.scidev.net/global/communication/feature/early-warning-of-disasters-facts-and-figures-1.html>

¹¹³ Monica Rozenfeld, “Twitter: An Early Disaster-Warning System” 11 September 2013,

<http://theinstitute.ieee.org/ieee-roundup/opinions/ieee-roundup/twitter-an-early-disasterwarning-system>

In order to determine the dispersion radius and to predict the underlying factors of a viral outbreak in a country, proper data collection is of major importance. This knowledge will be required to control an epidemic. Epidemiologists are able to obtain this information by performing surveillance, conduct descriptive studies and by implementing a lot of statistical analyses and prediction models on a large amount of data. Epidemiology refers to “*the study of the distribution and determinants of health-related states or events (including disease), and the application of this study to the control of diseases and other health problems.*”¹¹⁴ New media can be a helpful tool to conduct epidemiological research.

5.8.1 Background

John Snow laid the foundation of epidemiology in 1854. Around that time, the Soho district of London suffered from a cholera outbreak. Snow examined many people who felt ill to determine what symptoms they had in common and as a result he came to the conclusion that many people had drunk water from the same (Broad Street) pump. John Snow decided to clean the water with chlorine and to remove the handle of the pump, on behalf of the local vestrymen. This intervention brought an end to the cholera epidemic. Although Snow didn't find the bacteria which caused the Soho epidemic, he found the solution to prevent a recurrence of the epidemic.¹¹⁵ A remarkable thing is that Snow used all skills available to him and his colleagues to create a consistent theory which concerned all processes and mechanisms involved in the subjects of his study, instead of claiming one epidemiological method like modern epidemiologists do.¹¹⁶ He only used statistics to help confirm a theory that he had already established. Modern epidemiologists, in contrast, rely on a probabilistic, arithmetical, and empirical method to provide a theory.¹¹⁷ The customary statistical approach deals with the assessment of the performance of a prediction model, which means that their main objective is quantification of how close predictions are to the actual outcome.¹¹⁸ To predict the source and properties (such as the fatality rate, transmissibility, illness duration) of an infectious disease, an outbreak is often an enormous challenge due to the uncertainty of the completeness and quality of the data.¹¹⁹ For example, in the case of the current Ebola epidemic in West Africa it took three months before Ebola was determined as the cause of the outbreak. Nevertheless, it has been the 25th epidemic outbreak of the Ebola virus.¹²⁰

5.8.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

New media is an important source to provide information during an epidemic disaster. As a result of the fear of an infectious disease, a crowd of worried citizens, with symptoms similar to the real symptoms of the infectious disease, will manifest itself.¹²¹ These citizens will maybe or even probably visit the hospitals, but will also search on the Internet for relevant

¹¹⁴ WHO (2014). *Epidemiology*. Retrieved: October, 21, 2014. <http://www.who.int/topics/epidemiology/en/>

¹¹⁵ Cameron, D. & Jones, I. G. (1983). “John Snow, the Broad Street Pump and Modern Epidemiology”. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 12(4), pp. 393-396.

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

¹¹⁸ Steyerberg, E.W., Vickers, A.J., Cook, N.R., Gerds, T., Gonen, M., Obuchowski, N., Pencina, M.J., Kattan, M. W. (2010). “Assessing the Performance of Prediction Models: A framework for Traditional and Novel Measures”. *Epidemiology*, 21(1), pp. 128- 138.

¹¹⁹ Farrar J.J., & Piot, P. (2014). “The Ebola Emergency – Immediate Action, Ongoing Strategy”. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 371 (16), pp.1545-1546.

¹²⁰ Ibid.

¹²¹ Helsloot, I & S.C. Quinn (2009). *Citizen response to pandemics, authorities' nightmare or daydream?* Toronto: American Political Science Conference.

information about the symptoms of the epidemic or its spread. Furthermore, it is likely that they will also blog about this on new media. The increasing number of blogs often fills the gaps left by the traditional media (news reports, analyses, etc.).¹²² However, during an epidemic this information will be less accurate and more difficult to trust. Citizen journalism can be used by governments to get insight in the way in which individuals and communities are coping with the effects of the epidemic. Moreover, new media such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and many other platforms are the means for younger people to communicate. They often will not communicate via traditional means.¹²³ Earning public confidence of the society, by the use of traditional as well as modern digital media is an important condition for the authorities to get grip on rumours and to prevent social disorder during an epidemic.

5.9 INTEGRATION OF HETEROGENEOUS DATA

One of the greatest challenges in crisis and emergency management is how to handle the incomplete, contradictory and fuzzy information.¹²⁴ The aim of data integration is to merge relevant information from multiple data sources.¹²⁵ Data integration is the process of standardisation of data definitions and data structures, by using a common conceptual schema across a collection of heterogeneous data sources. Data that will be subjected to integration should first become consistent and compatible with different systems or databases.¹²⁶

5.9.1 Background

For source schemas belonging to heterogeneous sources, the specification of this mapping involves exploration of the semantics of data belonging to the source as well as the global schemas.¹²⁷ A framework for performing information integration over multiple sources is necessary.¹²⁸ Many scholars have advocated that a solid and consistent theoretical foundation for semantic integration (and information integration by enlarge) is abstract algebraic frameworks.¹²⁹ Information integration implies semantic integration, which, in turn, usually involves ontology integration. Among them, ontology mapping (definition and an early survey of approaches were given by Kalfoglou and Schorlemmer¹³⁰) and/or ontology merging are used as techniques of ontology integration so that semantically consistent information can be preserved and exchanged. For more advanced quests, translating between different logical

¹²² Booth, S. & Hills-Evans, K. (2009). *Pandemic Influenza. Preparation and response: A Citizen's Guide*. United States: InSTEDD.

¹²³ Ibid.

¹²⁴ Gang Kou, Yi Peng, Chunwei Lou, Yu Tang, Guoxun Wang, Shiming Li, "A heterogeneous information integration framework for emergency management", 2010 Page(s): 672 – 675, <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/articleDetails.jsp?tp=&arnumber=5534684&queryText%3DA+heterogeneous+information+integration+framework+for+emergency+management>

¹²⁵ "The research issues: Using Integrated data sources", Center for Technology in Government, 2003 http://www.ctg.albany.edu/publications/reports/multiple_data_sources?chapter=5&PrintVersion=2

¹²⁶ "Research and Practical Experiences in the Use of Multiple Data Sources", Center for Technology in Government, 2003,

http://www.ctg.albany.edu/publications/reports/multiple_data_sources/multiple_data_sources.pdf

¹²⁷ I. Kotsiopoulos, P. Rentzepopoulos, "Information Integration report – Bringing Together and Accelerating eGovernment Research in the EU", March 2009, http://www.epractice.eu/files/information_integration.pdf

¹²⁸ "The research issues: Using Integrated data sources", Center for Technology in Government, 2003 http://www.ctg.albany.edu/publications/reports/multiple_data_sources?chapter=5&PrintVersion=2

¹²⁹ I. Kotsiopoulos, P. Rentzepopoulos, "Information Integration report – Bringing Together and Accelerating eGovernment Research in the EU", March 2009, http://www.epractice.eu/files/information_integration.pdf

¹³⁰ Kalfoglou Y., Schorlemmer M., "Ontology mapping: the state of the art", Knowledge Engineering Review, 18(1): 1-31, 2003

systems, institution morphisms¹³¹ can be defined as well as morphisms of theories over different institutions^{132, 133}; these frameworks represent a most general abstract foundation for ontology integration.

Data integration alleviates the burden of gathering duplicated data and enables the extraction of information that would otherwise be impossible. For example, law enforcement agencies such as Interpol benefit from the ability to access integrated databases of various national police forces. Integrated data assist their effort in fighting and suppresses international terrorism and other criminal activities. Agencies like medical researchers and epidemiologists, will access records at once in order to find information across geographical and ethnic boundaries allowing a better prediction about certain diseases. In each case, information extracted from such integrated sources would have been impossible with data sources viewed in isolation.¹³⁴

5.9.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

During crises, it is important for stakeholders to receive information from multiple sources. It is unquestioned that social media constitute a source with significant information. Social media might be considered as a heterogeneous database as they include text, images and videos. An integrated data system accessing social media's databases is able to extract information related to natural disasters, diseases, terrorism and other types of crisis. As has been analyzed in deliverable D3.2.1¹³⁵, although a complete semantic model of all social media data would be a very powerful tool, so far no such model is available since standardisation of similarity is inappropriate, and also not evidenced in the market. Moreover, social media may operate independently as an integrated system. For example, Twitter could gather related hash tags in order to provide a further comprehensive view of critical situations.

As elaborated on in Deliverable 3.3.2 of COSMIC¹³⁶, an interesting development is that as crises have a relatively limited vocabulary, concepts and their inter-relations can be formalised as crisis ontologies and then utilised by possibly specific social media applications. In this respect, a variety of crisis specific ontologies are already in use, including the DiRes ontology by the European project Disaster 2.0.

5.10 INTERNET OF THINGS

The Internet of Things (IoT) as defined by technology analysts and visionaries is a network of physical objects accessed through the Internet. These objects contain embedded technology to interact with internal states or the external environment¹³⁷. IoT is a scenario in which objects

¹³¹ Goguen J., Rosu G., "Institution Morphisms", *Formal Aspects of Computing*, 13:274-387, 2002

¹³² Diaconescu R., "Grothendieck institutions", *Applied Categorical Structures*, 10:383-402, 2002.

¹³³ Goguen J., "Data, schema and ontology integration", in *Proceedings: Workshop on Combination of Logics*, pp 21-31, Center for Logic and Computation, Instituto Superior Tecnico, Lisbon, Portugal 2004

¹³⁴ "Research and Practical Experiences in the Use of Multiple Data Sources" Center for Technology in Government, 2003, and the references therein

http://www.ctg.albany.edu/publications/reports/multiple_data_sources/multiple_data_sources.pdf

¹³⁵ COSMIC, Deliverable D3.2.1, "Political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies", October 2013

¹³⁶ COSMIC Deliverable D3.3.2 "Final report on the strategic use of emerging communication technologies for crisis stakeholders", October 2014

¹³⁷ IT Glossary "Internet of Things", Gartner, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/internet-of-things/>

are provided with unique identifiers and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. Things, in the IoT, can refer to a wide variety of devices such as heart monitoring implants, biochip transponders, or any other natural or man-made object that can be assigned an IP address and be provided with the ability to transfer data over a network.¹³⁸

5.10.1 Background

The IoT connects new places, such as manufacturing floors, energy grids, healthcare facilities, and transportation systems, to the Internet. When an object can represent itself digitally, it can be controlled from anywhere.¹³⁹ For instance, as Hurricane Sandy hit the East Coast, Eagle Research Corporation worked with New Jersey Natural Gas (NJNG) in order to monitor more than 250 wireless devices, to identify, locate and repair damage to its pipeline and systems infrastructure, while remotely turned off the service to areas throughout the entire storm event.¹⁴⁰

Devices in IoT are able to communicate with other objects, identify themselves to other devices without requiring human interaction.¹⁴¹ One good example of an application of IoT technology was during the Japan nuclear catastrophe, when numerous instruments used for measuring ionising radiation owned by individuals were connected to the Internet to provide a detailed view of radiation levels across the country.¹⁴²

5.10.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Devices in IoT automatically detect a disaster before it occurs. A bridge, for example, could monitor the vibrations and the state of its material structure in order to ensure the security of vehicles using it.¹⁴³ In that case, should an unusual state be detected, the bridge would alert the authorities to take measures, for example having public access closed, if necessary. While 72% of all Internet users are now active on social media¹⁴⁴ such information could easily spread and prevent the public from trying to reach the bridge¹⁴⁵. Another benefit of an IoT device is that it can potentially minimise the time needed from the moment somebody identifies a crisis and the moment the alert reaches the wider public. In an IoT world, devices

¹³⁸ Ivy Wigmore, “Internet of Things”, June 2014,

<http://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/Internet-of-Things>

¹³⁹ “Internet of Things”, Cisco, <http://www.cisco.com/web/solutions/trends/iot/overview.html>

¹⁴⁰ Glenn Littman, “Weathering the Storm: Remote Monitoring and Control to Mitigate Disaster Event”, <http://www.remotemagazine.com/IoTWest/remote-2014-program/>

¹⁴¹ “Internet of Things”, June 2014 Ivy Wigmore <http://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/Internet-of-Things>

¹⁴² Ovidiu Vermesan, Peter Friess, “Internet of Things: Converging Technologies for Smart Environments and Integrated Ecosystems”, 2013, http://www.internet-of-things-research.eu/pdf/Converging_Technologies_for_Smart_Environments_and_Integrated_Ecosystems_IERC_Book_Open_Access_2013.pdf

¹⁴³ Jacob Morgan, “A Simple Explanation of the Internet of Things”, 13 May 2014,

<http://www.forbes.com/sites/jacobmorgan/2014/05/13/simple-explanation-internet-things-that-anyone-can-understand/>

¹⁴⁴ Jay Baer, “11 Shocking New Social Media Statistics in America”,

<http://www.convinceandconvert.com/social-media-research/11-shocking-new-social-media-statistics-in-america/df>

¹⁴⁵ Jacob Morgan, “A Simple Explanation of the Internet of Things”, 13 May 2014,

<http://www.forbes.com/sites/jacobmorgan/2014/05/13/simple-explanation-internet-things-that-anyone-can-understand/>

can sense the forthcoming crisis signals and automatically inform several organisations and (possibly) the public (via alerts on social media), thus requiring no human meditation.

5.11 MOBILE E-HEALTH

Mobile Health stands for the provision of health-related services using mobile communication technology. Modern information and communication technologies (ICTs), such as the internet, are not yet commonly available in resource-poor settings. The mobile phone is a notable exception as it is the first ICT tool that has reached even remote areas in low and middle income countries (LMIC). The coverage of mobile networks is increasing rapidly all over the world and the number of subscribers has exceeded undoubtedly the number of fixed-line connections in many LMIC in recent years.¹⁴⁶

5.11.1 Background

Mobile phones, particularly, and other mobile computing devices, are becoming increasingly ubiquitous; this enhances the potential to assess and improve public health. Through Mobile Health (mHealth) technologies, researchers have the ability to capture multiple sources of health data, detailed information about physical activity, physiological responses, such as, for example, through small sensors attached to the body and connected wirelessly to the telecommunications network. Further, the accessibility and data availability of mHealth methodologies could be utilised to change public health and health care on a large scale, for example, by employing mobile tools to decrease the number of people who develop diabetes, prevent falls at home, and help those who need medication to keep to dosage schedules.¹⁴⁷

While nothing is a more definitive way to assess health than visiting a doctor, many applications allow individuals to assess and research about their symptoms; read about conditions, medications, and procedures; view important news in health; look for a variety of types of medical facilities; and book an appointment with speed and ease. These applications manifest their usefulness in a convincing way even in serious medical emergencies.¹⁴⁸

Social media sites are also helping patients cope with specific diseases. For example, diabetes-related complications represent a major source of emergency room visits. A study of a site such as www.TuDiabetes.org has around 500 patients report their experience with hypoglycemic events, use of insulin pumps, and health issues. The average person reports they had suffered six insulin-related problems. From sharing their experience, viewers could see what others had experienced and ways to cope with particular health emergencies.¹⁴⁹

5.11.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Many applications are designed to support patients in emergency situations. Applications such as iWander are being used for patients suffering from Alzheimer's disease or dementia. The

¹⁴⁶“What is mHealth?”.Royal tropical institute <http://mhealthinfo.org/what-mhealth>

¹⁴⁷ “mHealth - Mobile Health Technologies”, National Institutes of Health Office of behavioral and social science research, http://obssr.od.nih.gov/scientific_areas/methodology/mhealth/

¹⁴⁸ “10 Things Your Phone Can Do in Emergency Situations”, Sharon Housley <http://www.notepage.net/learning-center/10-things-your-phone-can-do-in-emergencies.htm>

¹⁴⁹ Errol Ozdalga, Ark Ozdalga, and Neera Ahuja, “The Smartphone in Medicine”, Journal of Medical Internet Research, Volume 14, September 27, 2012, <http://www.jmir.org/2012/5/e128/>

application runs in the background and collects data from the device's sensors such as GPS, time of day, weather condition, stage of dementia and user feedback. This data is then evaluated using network techniques to determine the probability that a person is wandering. Depending on the probability, iWander automatically takes action to help navigate the patient to a safe location, notify caregivers, provide the current location of the patient and call an emergency number such as 911 in the US.¹⁵⁰ Such applications may help not only patients but also people with disabilities involved in a crisis situation. People with disabilities are generally more vulnerable during disasters and public emergencies than the general population. Physical, sensory and cognitive impairments may result in greater difficulty in receiving and understanding emergency alert information, and greater difficulty in taking appropriate action. In the US, the considerable growth of social media has generated increasing interest from national, state and local authorities in leveraging these channels to communicate public health and safety information.¹⁵¹

5.12 NATURAL LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY

In computing, natural language refers to a human language such as English, Russian, and German etc. as distinct from the artificial programming language with which a programmer usually interacts with a computer. The term usually refers to a written language but might also apply to spoken language.¹⁵² There is still considerable technical difficulty in designing and implementing automated computerised systems that can “understand” natural language. Despite the progress made there are still no well-defined solutions to this problem.

5.12.1 Background

The development of Natural language processing (NLP) applications is challenging: machines are designed to “understand” programming languages that are naturally precise, unambiguous and highly structured. Human speech, however, is often ambiguous and the linguistic structure depends on many complex variables, including slang, regional dialects and social context. NLP is generally defined as the ability of a computer program to understand human speech as spoken.¹⁵³

Application areas within NLP include automatic translation machines between languages; dialogue systems, which allow communication with a machine using natural language; and information extraction, where the goal is to transform unstructured text into structured representations that can be searched and browsed in flexible ways. NLP technologies are having a dramatic impact on the way people interact with computers and each other through the language, and on the way people access the vast amount of linguistic data in electronic form.¹⁵⁴ The ultimate goal of NLP systems is simple to define: a human addressing a computer as though he was addressing another person.¹⁵⁵

¹⁵⁰ Frank Sposaro, Justin Danielson, Gary Tyson, “iWander: An Android Application for Dementia Patients”, <http://ww2.cs.fsu.edu/~sposaro/publications/iWander.pdf>

¹⁵¹ John T. Morris, James L. Mueller, Michael L. Jones “Use of Social Media During Public Emergencies by People With Disabilities”, pp 567-574, 15 May 2014, <http://www.medscape.com/viewarticle/831276>

¹⁵² Margaret Rouse, “Natural Language”, September 2005 <http://whatistechtarget.com/definition/natural-language>

¹⁵³ Ibid

¹⁵⁴ “Natural Language Processing”, Coursera, <https://www.coursera.org/course/nlangp>

¹⁵⁵ “Natural Language Processing”, Microsoft Research, <http://research.microsoft.com/en-us/groups/nlp/>

5.12.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Natural Language Technologies (NLTs) constitute an important factor in crisis management. Since the course of a crisis is anchored on harvesting information, NLTs are able to automatically summarise information, create new texts by combining multiple documents and search engines.¹⁵⁶ During a disaster the phone calls between victims and stakeholders include valuable information. NLTs have the unique ability of converting spoken speech into text with a view to avoid information loss.¹⁵⁷ Social networks are facing a similar information loss problem owing to the vast amount of data. NLTs should be able to analyze language patterns to understand text. One of the most compelling ways NLTs offer valuable intelligence is by tracking sentiment – the tone of a written message (tweet, facebook update, etc.) – and tag that text as positive, negative or neutral.¹⁵⁸ Such technology could cooperate with social media in order to tag tweets and posts of high importance during crises.

5.13 OPEN DATA

According to the *open definition*¹⁵⁹, “a piece of data or content is open if anyone is free to use, reuse, and redistribute it — subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and/or share-alike.” Scientific and other data has long existed that conforms to this definition, but the modern open data movement is connected to digital communications and the Internet; when we work with open data, we normally expect it to be accessible online, with the additional implication that the data is represented in a usable format that can be understood and processed by anybody accessing the data.

5.13.1 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Open data can play a very important role in crisis management. Evidence provided by Stauffacher et al.¹⁶⁰ indicates that open data can significantly improve crisis management including in response to major disasters, and that governments and major NGOs are making very important progress in actually adopting and enacting open data policies; example cases include crises in Haiti, Afghanistan, Uganda and Kenya. It is important to note that tools supporting open data are appearing, for example opendatakit, a “free and open-source set of tools which help organisations author, field, and manage mobile data collection solutions”^{161,162}, which can then be published as open data and exploited in support of crisis management e.g. following a Web 3.0 approach¹⁶³.

¹⁵⁶ Brandon Smietana, “How does natural language processing work?”, April 2010,

<http://www.quora.com/How-does-natural-language-processing-work>

¹⁵⁷ Ibid

¹⁵⁸ John Rehlingvon, “How Natural Language Processing Helps Uncover Social Media Sentiment”, August 2011, <http://mashable.com/2011/11/08/natural-language-processing-social-media/>

¹⁵⁹ <http://opendefinition.org/>

¹⁶⁰ Daniel Stauffacher, Sanjana Hattotuwa and Barbara Weekes, “The potential and challenges of open data for crisis information management and aid efficiency”, ICT4Peace Foundation, March 2012, <http://ict4peace.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/The-potential-and-challenges-of-open-data-for-crisis-information-management-and-aid-efficiency.pdf>

¹⁶¹ <http://opendatakit.org/>

¹⁶² Hartung, Carl, et al. “Open data kit: Tools to build information services for developing regions.” Proceedings of the 4th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies and Development. ACM, 2010.

¹⁶³ Schulz, Axel, Heiko Paulheim, and Florian Probst. “Crisis information management in the web 3.0 age.” 9th International ISCRAM Conference. 2012.

The implications of open data for social networks and crises have been linked to interoperability and standards in COSMIC deliverables D3.2.2 and D3.3.2.

5.14 “ORGANIC” OR SMARTPHONE SENSOR NETWORKS

Situational awareness is a key factor in crisis management, and measuring the environment in which a crisis or disaster is imminent or ongoing or where it has previously struck, is a key technical capability. Networks of smartphones offer a very important opportunity for real-time and highly-detailed measurement of environments populated by smartphone users. However, technical as well as legal and ethical challenges remain to be solved for “organic” or smartphone sensor networks to be fully exploited.

5.14.1 Background

Wireless Sensor Networks are a hugely promising technology limited predominantly by one core problem: energy consumption¹⁶⁴. Wireless Sensor Networks integrate sensors with wireless communication capabilities and an autonomous energy supply – usually a battery. This enables the creation of a network of sensors, which function autonomously to cover the geographical space in which they are distributed, monitoring their environment according to the specific sensors that have been deployed (which can be e.g. a thermometer, barometre, or also a microphone or camera), and forming ad-hoc wireless networks to transmit measurements back to some data collection point. Valuable application areas include “Physiological monitoring; Environmental monitoring (air, water, soil chemistry); Condition based maintenance; Smart spaces; Military; Precision agriculture; Transportation; Factory instrumentation and inventory tracking, [and] Habitat monitoring”¹⁶⁵. Detailed monitoring of the environment is clearly a critically useful capability during a crisis. However, the aforementioned problem of energy consumption greatly limits the commercially and practically viable application scenarios for Wireless Sensor Networks.

Smartphones are mobile devices that often integrate a rich selection of sensors¹⁶⁶. Smartphone owners recharge their smartphones in order to keep them operational – thus directly solving the energy problem, and offering an improved version of Wireless Sensor Networks¹⁶⁷ for a potentially broad range of applications, when considering regions densely populated by smartphone users and when the required measurements can be made by the devices in use. On the other hand, smartphones are not primarily intended for use as nodes in sensor networks – there is no guarantee regarding where a smartphone owner will take and use her/his device, and the issue of privacy needs to be resolved in order for a data aggregator to pull measurements from individual users’ devices. Nevertheless, the vast number of smartphones in use around the world offers many opportunities for valuable data to be (legally) collected from them and put to a variety of important uses. Applications of “organic” or smartphone

¹⁶⁴ Anastasi, Giuseppe, et al. "Energy conservation in wireless sensor networks: A survey." *Ad Hoc Networks* 7.3 (2009): 537-568.

¹⁶⁵ Estrin, Deborah, et al. "Instrumenting the world with wireless sensor networks." *Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, 2001. Proceedings.(ICASSP'01). 2001 IEEE International Conference on. Vol. 4. IEEE, 2001.

¹⁶⁶ see COSMIC project, Deliverable D2.1

¹⁶⁷ note that the communication paradigm in this case is different: Wireless Sensor Networks form ad-hoc wireless networks in order to transmit measurements, whereas smartphones are connected to data networks through commercial or other telephony services

sensor networks have included tracking and analysis of CO₂ emissions¹⁶⁸, measurement of traffic¹⁶⁹, and monitoring of cardiac patients¹⁷⁰. An application related to traffic monitoring has been to detect accidents and provide information to first responders^{171,172}, which may be possible to be generalised to large scale crises. Finally, measurements for tracking the ecological impact of the Gulf Oil spill have also been made using a network of smartphones¹⁷³.

Figure 11: “Transforming Mobile Phones into Sensor Networks”¹⁷⁴

We should note that designing and validating measurement systems relying on “organic” or smartphone sensor networks is technically challenging, and research in this direction is ongoing¹⁷⁵. We expect new and important applications to emerge regularly in the near future.

5.14.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Since “organic” or smartphone sensor networks are capable of providing a very rich environmental monitoring capability, they are highly promising for crisis management. They enable the measurement of physical environmental conditions (e.g. as relevant to weather prediction) in an extremely fine granularity. However, as the aforementioned applications to detecting and reporting traffic accidents and to tracking the environmental impact of the gulf

¹⁶⁸ Froehlich, Jon, et al. "UbiGreen: investigating a mobile tool for tracking and supporting green transportation habits." Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. ACM, 2009.

¹⁶⁹ Rose, Geoff. "Mobile phones as traffic probes: practices, prospects and issues." Transport Reviews 26.3 (2006): 275-291.

¹⁷⁰ Leijdekkers, Peter, and Valerie Gay. "Personal heart monitoring and rehabilitation system using smart phones." Mobile Business, 2006. ICMB'06. International Conference on. IEEE, 2006.

¹⁷¹ Thompson, Chris, et al. "Optimizing mobile application performance with model-driven engineering." Software Technologies for Embedded and Ubiquitous Systems. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009. 36-46.

¹⁷² Jones, Willie D. "Forecasting traffic flow." Spectrum, IEEE 38.1 (2001): 90-91.

¹⁷³ Gahrn, A. "Reporting on the gulf oil spill from your cell phone.", CNN (2010), <http://www.cnn.com/2010/TECH/mobile/06/11/oil.spil.app/index.html>

¹⁷⁴ <http://www.atelier.net/en/trends/articles/transforming-mobile-phones-sensor-networks>

¹⁷⁵ Turner, Hamilton, and Jules White. "Verification and Validation of Smartphone Sensor Networks." Mobile Wireless Middleware, Operating Systems, and Applications. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012. 233-247.

oil spill demonstrate, situational awareness about the status of disaster-affected individuals and regions can also be generated. If the related privacy issues can be resolved, so as to provide valuable intelligence for exclusive use in managing crises, without violating smartphone owners' privacy, extremely extensive data collection can be enabled through this technology. Furthermore, there is a trend to integrate ever more sensors on smartphones¹⁷⁶. As the sensing capabilities of smartphones expand, so will the potential value of networks of such devices.

5.15 PATTERN ANALYSIS AND MACHINE INTELLIGENCE

Pattern recognition is the scientific discipline whose goal is the classification of objects into a number of categories or classes. Depending on the application, these objects can be images or signal waveforms or any type of measurements that need to be classified. Pattern recognition is an integral part of most machine intelligence systems built for decision making.¹⁷⁷

5.15.1 Background

Pattern is a set of objects or phenomena or concepts where the elements of the set are similar to one another in certain ways or aspects. The patterns are described by certain quantities, qualities, traits and notable features. Pattern Recognition (PR) consists of recognising a pattern using a machine usually a computer and can be defined in several ways. It is a study of ideas and algorithms that provide computers with a perceptual capability to put abstract objects, or patterns into categories in a simple and reliable way. PR covers a wide spectrum of disciplines such as Cybernetics, Computer Science, Electronics, Psychology and Philosophy. PR is an important aspect of applying computers to solve problems in science and engineering, since many of them involve analysis and classification of measurements, taken from physical processes.¹⁷⁸

When tackling intelligence from the machine perspective, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become one of the main fields of interest. To be considered as an intelligent machine, the machine has to be able to interact with the environment autonomously. Interacting with the environment involves both learning from it and adapting to its changes. This characteristic differentiates normal machines from intelligent machines. A normal machine has a specific programmed set of tasks in which it will execute accordingly. On the other hand, an intelligent machine has a goal to achieve, and it is equipped with a learning mechanism to help realise the desired goal.¹⁷⁹

5.15.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Artificial intelligence technology tries to improve the efficiency of the management process during crisis response via: robotics sustaining urban search and rescue operations, enhancing

¹⁷⁶ this is also discussed further in the section on wearable sensors

¹⁷⁷ Sergios Theodoridis, Konstantinos Koutroumbas, "Pattern Recognition". Academic Press. Second Edition <http://worldtracker.org/media/library/Electronics%20and%20Communications/Electronics%20ebook%20collection%20II/THEODORIDIS,%20S.%20%20282002%29.%20Pattern%20Recognition%20%282nd%20ed.%29.pdf>

¹⁷⁸ C. N. Ravi Kumar, "Pattern Classification", University of Mysore, [http://uni-mysore.ac.in/Asc/2011/RC%202011/2%20RC%20in%20Mathematical%20Science%20\(9-1-12%20to%2029-1-12\)/Information%20by%20Resource%20Person/Prof.%20C.N.%20Ravi%20Kumar/SIT_PC.ppt](http://uni-mysore.ac.in/Asc/2011/RC%202011/2%20RC%20in%20Mathematical%20Science%20(9-1-12%20to%2029-1-12)/Information%20by%20Resource%20Person/Prof.%20C.N.%20Ravi%20Kumar/SIT_PC.ppt)

¹⁷⁹ Lakhmi C. Jain, Anas Quteishat, and Chee Peng Lim, "Intelligent Machines: An Introduction" Springer, , <http://www.springer.com/engineering/computational+intelligence+and+complexity/book/978-3-540-72695-1>

information sharing using ontologies, providing customised query to crisis actors, and providing multi-agent systems for real time support and simulated environments.¹⁸⁰ Social media platforms are increasingly used to communicate crisis information when major disasters strike. Artificial Intelligence for Disaster Response (AIDR) platforms are in existence today. They aim to leverage machine learning to automatically identify informative content on media such as Twitter and Facebook during disasters, thus overcoming some of the limitations which are due to multiple meanings depending on context and language.¹⁸¹

5.16 PROFILING SOCIAL MEDIA USERS

Thanks to the development of the Web 2.0 technology, it is possible to interact and collaborate with citizens by means of using social media platforms. A wide public use social media. However, more people with similar personal characteristics or interests make use of one or more specific social networking platforms. It is obviously important for business organisations and government agencies to map which people will make use of which specific social network platform in order to (be able to) communicate effectively. For example, the average number of social network platforms used is correlating with age, older people, one average, make less use of social network platforms.¹⁸² There are both online as well as offline methods for mapping user profiles (and user journeys) of a specific social media platform.

5.16.1 Background

Profiling is the practice of creating a profile of something, someone or of a specific group of people. A profile consists of specific characteristics, which most times represent an individual. Profiles are used for different purposes. For example, one controversial form of profiling is racial profiling, which assumed to be one of the working methods of the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI, USA) in their ‘‘The war on Terror’’.¹⁸³ Racial profiling refers to ‘*the use of personal characteristics to determine whether a person maybe engaged in illegal activity.*’¹⁸⁴ People also make personal profiles on social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn to present themselves and to connect and interact with each other, all the while, creating and exchanging therefore a lot of user-generated-content (UGC).¹⁸⁵ Private and public organisations also make use of social media platforms to get feedback on their activities and for example to mobilise customers to buy a particular product. In order to reach a relevant group of people it is necessary to analyse the characteristics of the descent of the UGC and, furthermore, to get an image of the people who use the social media platforms. The most common method for profiling social media users are online or off-line surveys.¹⁸⁶ An example of an offline survey is a study of the Statistics Netherlands (CBS).

¹⁸⁰ Khaled M. Khalil, M. Abdel-Aziz, Taymour T. Nazmy & Abdel-Badeeh M. Salem, ‘‘The role of artificial intelligence technologies in crisis response’’, <http://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0806/0806.1280.pdf>.

¹⁸¹ ‘‘AIDR: Artificial Intelligence for Disaster Response’’, [iRevolution](http://irevolution.net/2013/10/01/aidr-artificial-intelligence-for-disaster-response/), 1 October 2013

¹⁸² Newcom Research & Consultancy B.V. (2014). Nationale Sociale Media Onderzoek 2014: Het grootste trendonderzoek van Nederland naar het gebruik en verwachting van social media. Zwolle: MarketingOost.

¹⁸³ New York Times (2014). Profiling Rules Said to Give F.B.I. Tactical. Retrieved: October, 24, 2014. http://www.nytimes.com/2014/04/10/us/profiling-rules-said-to-give-fbi-tactical-leeway.html?_r=0

¹⁸⁴ Dictionary (2014). Profiling. October, 23, 2014. <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/profiling>

¹⁸⁵ Kaplan, A.M. & Haenlein, M. (2010). ‘‘Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media’’. *Business Horizons*, 53 (1), pp. 59-68.

¹⁸⁶ Kahrimanovic (2014). Inzicht krijgen in de user journey: focusgroep, diepteinterview of allebei? October, 22, 2014.

This study maps which people make use of a social medium platforms. The participants of this study were asked by telephone about their use of social media and for what reasons they use social media platforms.¹⁸⁷ An example of an online survey is the study of Newcom by which approximately 15000 people were asked online to complete a questionnaire, with the aim to provide insight into the use of social media platforms relating to different age categories.¹⁸⁸ While these questionnaires mainly gave insight into social media use concerning different age categories, there're also studies that reveal more detailed characteristics of social media users. For example Ross et al. have studied (by conducting an online survey) how Facebook use is associated with personal characteristics and competencies. They showed that personality (Five-factor model) had a small influence on the use of Facebook. For example, respondents who were identified as extravert appeared to be more enrolled in Facebook groups, and respondents with a high score on neuroticism preferred using the Facebook wall, respondents that scored low on neuroticism preferred posting photo's on their Facebook profile. Moreover competency factors, such as motivation, correlated with the frequency of Facebook use and the duration of a Facebook visit.¹⁸⁹

5.16.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Profiling social media users by collecting user information with offline or online methods can be of major importance for crisis managers. Profiling is especially important for crisis communication professionals, regarding to informing a specific group of people by the correct social media platform, for example nearby residents of a disaster site. In the case of the EHEC outbreak in Germany in 2011, it appeared that students during an epidemic made more use of information from websites (i.e. UGC) rather than of traditional media (newspapers and TV channels). An explanation for this is that they are part of the age category which uses social media platforms the most on a daily basis. This implies that it is important for emergency services to get insight in what people can be reached by different social media platforms.¹⁹⁰

5.17 REPORTING AND ALERTS SERVICES

In contemporary society there is an abundance of information and ever increasing possibilities to process this data. Monitoring and predicting all kinds of threats is consequently commonplace for governments as well as many companies, resulting in services to report directly on these insights and predictions, for example by issuing an alarm with or without an advice on how to react.

<http://www.frankwatching.com/archive/2014/10/06/inzicht-krijgen-in-de-user-journey-focusgroep-diepte-interview-of-allebei/>

¹⁸⁷ Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2013). Bevolkingstrends 2013: Gebruik en gebruikers van sociale media. October, 23. <http://www.cbs.nl/NR/rdonlyres/06A12225-495E-4620-80F6-F2A53E819957/0/20131001b15art.pdf>

¹⁸⁸ Newcom Research & Consultancy B.V. (2014). *Nationale Sociale Media Onderzoek 2014: Het grootste trendonderzoek van Nederland naar het gebruik en verwachting van social media*. Zwolle: Marketing Oost.

¹⁸⁹ Ross, C., Orr, E.S., Sasic, M., Arsenault, J.M., Simmering, M.G., Orr, R. R.(2009). 'Personality and motivations associated with Facebook use'. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 25 (2), pp. 578-586.

¹⁹⁰ Velsen, L. van, Beaujean, D.J.M.A., Gemert-Peijnen, L. van, Wentzel, J., Steenbergen, J.E. van (2012). 'Gebruik van nieuwe media tijdens een infectieziekte-uitbraak: Een analyse van de EHEC-uitbraak in 2011'. *Infectieziekten Bulletin*, 23 (7), pp. 194-197.

5.17.1 Background

In the modern days the ways in which the public can be alerted and informed have drastically increased and developed from acoustic measures such as sirens, traditional media and person to person communications on site or through landlines. A major contributor is the widespread usage of mobile phones, which allows for techniques like cell broadcasting and location based Short Message Services (SMS) where messages are sent to every active mobile phone in the particular area.¹⁹¹ The even more sophisticated *smartphones* as well as tablets provide a medium for internet related communication, for example through social media like Twitter and Facebook. Additionally most alerting services also offer downloadable applications to receive these reports directly on your mobile device. New communication technologies such as matrix signs that normally offer traffic information provide a very different venue for broadcasting alerts. The European initiative AmberAlert exemplifies a modern service which spreads missing children reports through several media outlets as just mentioned.¹⁹²

Most of these systems one-sidedly transmit information, they focus on alerting civilians and offering them relevant information or an action perspective. Nonetheless there are also systems in place which offer venues for the receiving party to send relevant information as well as systems that alert the ‘owner’ of relevant information becoming available. The latter entails information pushing devices such as RSS feeds, which are increasingly used by doctors to notify them of new relevant insight becoming available. An RRS reader provides them with an organised collection of evidence presented in a single interface.¹⁹³

5.17.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Alerting and reporting services play a significant role during crisis management, a role that is exponentially increasing with the new technological advances.

Several governments already broadly use (modern) alerting systems during large scale incidents to inform civilians and offer them an action perspective. To this end the Dutch government for example uses NL-Alert, which uses cell broadcasting and RijnmondVeilig.nl, which employs various media to spread relevant information to civilians.¹⁹⁴ This potential is however not restricted to government-civilian communication, which is shown by the Dutch ‘alert4omgevingen’.¹⁹⁵ An application that offers a venue for emergency response officials to report an incident, accompanied by the relevant information, that subsequently notifies other emergency response officials and companies which subsequently can provide aid. Such initiatives can be added on to and deployed more widely throughout the world since many countries are not yet making use of these sophisticated possibilities. Additionally information pushing services might be able to serve data gathering efforts and early warning systems.

5.18 ROBOTS AND DRONES

¹⁹¹ Civil Contingencies Secretariat (2014). *Mobile Alerting Trials: Project Final Report*. London: U.K., Cabinet Office.

¹⁹² Bouwmeester, J., Das, E., Franx, K. en Holzmann, M. (2013). *Behoeftenonderzoek alerteringssystemen* (2013-1925). I&O Research: Hoorn

¹⁹³ Giustini, D. (2006). “How Web 2.0 is changing medicine: is a medical Wikipedia the next step?”. *BMJ*. 333, pp. 1283-1284

¹⁹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁹⁵ Centric. (2014) *BHV calamiteiten alerteringssysteem: alert4omgevingen*. Retrieved: October 20, 2014. <http://www.centric.eu/NL/Default/Software-Solutions/Standaardsoftware/Calamiteiten-alerteringssysteem>

Robotics is the science of designing and building machines that are programmed to perform more than one function traditionally performed by humans.¹⁹⁶ The work that robots do is classified into three major categories: assembly and finishing of products; movement of materials and objects; and performance of work in environmentally difficult or hazardous situations.¹⁹⁷ Drones are probably the most advanced equipment in the field of robotics, aeronautics and electronics. The technical name of drones is Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVS), which are either controlled by “pilots” from the ground or, increasingly, autonomously following a pre-programmed mission.¹⁹⁸

5.18.1 Background

Robots are capable of a variety of tasks humans cannot perform either due to danger or to a certain level of repetition. The military and the scientific community have utilised robots for operation in deadly for humans situations or reconnaissance missions in severe conditions, while the medical community uses robots to perform delicate operations difficult for a human hand.¹⁹⁹ Robots have a variety of capabilities in fields such as healthcare, home care, security, agriculture, transportation and the environment.²⁰⁰ For example, an underwater robot is able to inspect and repair underwater pipelines.²⁰¹ The robot is controlled from the surface with simple instructions, and it has to interact with the uncertainty and unpredictability of the environmental conditions to complete a given task.

Drones have been invented to carry out critical tasks and missions.²⁰² Typically, an UAV comprises onboard processing capabilities, vision, satellite (e.g. Global Positioning System) navigation, and wireless communication. One of the main functions of an UAV is to navigate in an uncontrolled, and often unknown environment, safely, and, at the same time, to perform the required task.²⁰³ What makes an UAV intelligent is the ability to fly to the target under varying conditions. As it is not possible to predict all possible navigation scenarios in one programme, the UAV has to learn from its environment and adapt to the changes as they occur in order to reach its destination.²⁰⁴

The use of drones has grown quickly in recent years because unlike manned aircraft drones are capable of staying aloft for many hours. Drones have lower cost than military aircraft and they are flown remotely so there is no danger to the flight crew.²⁰⁵ Besides military use,

¹⁹⁶ “Robotics - Historical Background, Robots At Work: The Present Day, Movement Of Materials, Hazardous Or Remote Duty Robots”, Science Encyclopaedia, <http://science.jrank.org/pages/5904/Robotics.html>

¹⁹⁷ “Robotics - Robots At Work: The Present Day”, Science Encyclopedia, <http://science.jrank.org/pages/5897/Robotics-Robots-at-work-present-day.html>

¹⁹⁸ Chris Cole , Jim Wright, “What are drones?”, January 2010, <http://dronewars.net/aboutdrone/>

¹⁹⁹“What Can Robots Do That Humans Can't”, Jason Chavis, eHow Contributor, http://www.ehow.com/about_4588118_robots-do-that-humans-cant.html

²⁰⁰“What Robots Can For you”, European Commission 03/06/2014 http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-14-386_en.htm

²⁰¹ “Intelligent Machines: An Introduction”, Lakhmi C. Jain, Anas Quteishat, and Chee Peng Lim, Springer, , <http://www.springer.com/engineering/computational+intelligence+and+complexity/book/978-3-540-72695-1>

²⁰² “Intelligent Machines: An Introduction”, Lakhmi C. Jain, Anas Quteishat, and Chee Peng Lim, Springer, , <http://www.springer.com/engineering/computational+intelligence+and+complexity/book/978-3-540-72695-1>

²⁰³ “Intelligent Machines: An Introduction”, Lakhmi C. Jain, Anas Quteishat, and Chee Peng Lim, Springer, <http://www.springer.com/engineering/computational+intelligence+and+complexity/book/978-3-540-72695-1>

²⁰⁴ “Intelligent Machines: An Introduction”, Lakhmi C. Jain, Anas Quteishat, and Chee Peng Lim Springer, , <http://www.springer.com/engineering/computational+intelligence+and+complexity/book/978-3-540-72695-1>

²⁰⁵“What are drones?”, Chris Cole ,Jim Wright, January 2010, <http://dronewars.net/aboutdrone/>

drones participate in various civilian operations such as search and rescue, weather analysis and surveillance. They have proven reliable, precise and hard to detect (stealth features).²⁰⁶

5.18.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Proven useful in past disasters such as Hurricane Sandy in 2012 and Typhoon Haiyan in 2013, UAVs/drones have advanced the field of disaster preparedness and relief. Before drones, there were manned helicopters which needed highly trained staff to fly while putting human lives at risk; they could not produce real-time information and had to fly at a certain height as to not to be affected by the disaster. Drones have offered a solution to these issues. They provide a bird's-eye-view of the affected area in high resolution, both during and after a storm. Drones can provide immediate access to unsafe areas with infrared and aerial imagery, offering emergency responders key information regarding damage, and can also help in bringing aid and relief to those in need.

Robotics is also on the forefront of the newest emergency management technology. Robots are designed to be relied on as replacements of a first-responder in dangerous situations. The technology within the robots enables the operator to 'tell' the robot what to do through its sensory devices. This allows the operator to control the robot remotely and complete the task as safely as possible.²⁰⁷ Robots provide a variety of functions in the crisis context, such as area exploration, mapping and expediting the search for victims.²⁰⁸ Emergency responders enhance the resiliency of communities by exploiting remotely operated robots to protect the public during extremely hazardous situations, including disabling or dismantling improvised explosive devices (pipes, packages, vehicles); searching for survivors in collapsed or compromised structures; establishing situational awareness during police actions; monitoring large scale industrial or transportation accidents; and mitigating potential terrorist attacks using chemical, biological, or radiological sources. Responders need capable robotic systems to be remotely operated from safe stand-off distances.²⁰⁹ Additionally, since robots and drones are connected to the Internet, in case of emergency, they can inform the public without human interaction. Information and photographs from the scene of the disaster can be automatically posted on social media, thus providing a more precise and truthful view of the situation.

5.19 SECURE COMMUNICATIONS AND TRUSTWORTHY ICT

For the ICT industry, the term trustworthy ICT refers to ICT infrastructure, services and technologies that can be trusted. It encompasses both communications infrastructures (networks, network equipment, network security, wired and wireless, social, business and legal context), appliances (mobile and traditional computing equipment, internet of things), applications (software running on this equipment and on the network, both business applications controlling and maintaining business processes, industrial applications

²⁰⁶“Robotics and Drones”, Tech and Law Center <http://www.techandlaw.net/areas-of-interest/drones-robotics.html>

²⁰⁷ “The Future of Disaster Response: Dogs, Drones and Robots”, Adjusters International, October 7, 2014 <http://adjustersinternational.com/articles/future-disaster-response-dogs-drones-robots/>

²⁰⁸“The role of artificial intelligence technologies in crisis response”, Khaled M. Khalil, M. Abdel-Aziz, Taymour T. Nazmy & Abdel-Badeeh M. Salem <http://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0806/0806.1280.pdf>

²⁰⁹“Emergency Response Robots”, Adam Jacoff, Hui-Min Huang, Ann Virts, October 1, 2013 <http://www.nist.gov/el/isd/ms/err.cfm>

controlling machines and industrial processes, web sites, ERP and CRM systems) and services (monitoring, business processing, data transformation, advisory, etc).²¹⁰

5.19.1 Background

Threats to critical infrastructures and national systems often become critical within days or even hours. Enabling a truly secure environment becomes even more complex as governments and businesses invest more in mobility, collaboration, cloud, and other forms of virtualisation. As new attacks are made by malevolent actors, verifiable trustworthiness in systems is vital for today's multi-threat environments. Trusting networks requires safe ICT to be built along them, with security being a foundational priority, spanning product security development to delivery and support.²¹¹

As databases of sensitive information become increasingly accessible on-line, the consequences of a security failure multiply. Rather than stealing a single social security or credit card number, a determined, skilled, and criminally inclined hacker might succeed in gaining access to files that contain identifying information for thousands of individuals. The same ease of access that makes electronic access to databases attractive in the first place could permit a malefactor to download large amounts of sensitive information or carry out hundreds of illegal transactions in seconds, perhaps too quickly for authorities to recognise or to plug a breach.²¹²

The technology to support secure communications today exists. Similarly, the physical and commercial infrastructure for widespread digital communication, the public switched network, Internet service providers, and similar components, already exist or are being built. The reasons making a communication system secure are the denial of access to unauthorised users, the encouragement to authorised users to be security-conscious, for example by changing their passwords on a regular basis and monitoring who accesses what data, and for what purposes.²¹³ A significant aspect in security communications is identification and authentication. As Russell and Gangemi put it: “Identification is the way to tell the system who you are. Authentication is the way to prove to the system, that you are, who you say you are. In just about any multi-user system, you must identify yourself, and the system must authenticate your identity, before you can use the system.”²¹⁴ Passwords are still, far and away, the authentication tool of choice. Even when authentication devices like tokens and biometric devices are used, they are usually supplements to, and not replacements for conventional login IDs and passwords. Biometrics and key cards typically act only as a first line of defense against intruders, not as the sole defense.²¹⁵

5.19.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

²¹⁰ “About Trustworthy ICT”, Workshop on measurability of trustworthiness, Brussels 03/09 ,source: FIRE Getaway to trustworthy ICT innovations in Europe <http://www.trustworthyictonfire.com/about-top/trustworthy-ict>

²¹¹ “Cisco Trustworthy Systems”, Cisco http://www.cisco.com/web/solutions/trends/trustworthy_systems/indepth.html

²¹² C. Richard Neu, Robert H. Anderson, Tora K. Bikson, “E-Mail Communication Between Government and Citizens”, http://www.rand.org/pubs/issue_papers/IP178/index2.html

²¹³ D. Russell & G.T. Gangemi, Sr., “Computer Security Basics”, 1st Edition, July 1991 <http://books.google.gr/books?id=DyrLV0kZEd8C&printsec=frontcover&hl=el#v=onepage&q&f=false>

²¹⁴ Ibid

²¹⁵ Ibid

Coombs claims that “crises are unpredictable and pose significant threats with the capability to harm an organisation.”²¹⁶ Technology plays a major role in most organisations; likewise, technology is an important aspect in crisis management. Moskowitz et al stress that during a crisis, technology helps ease communications, knowledge transfer and management, and decision support.²¹⁷, and this applies to information and communications technology (ICT) in particular.^{218, 219}

In disaster cases, communication between authorities and between citizens and authorities should be through trustworthy ICT in order to avoid misinformation and rumors which could increase the public's panic. Social media can be considered as a trustworthy ICT since they provide security features. For example, a Facebook user can enable the “Login Notification” so that whenever anybody (or a hacker) tries to login with the same user ID and password, he will receive a notification on his cell phone.²²⁰ Many social networks today make users aware of their personal information and encourage them to report on another user or account where malicious activity has been detected.

During a crisis, social media users can search for authorised, official accounts in order to be updated and avoid misinformation.

5.20 SENSOR INFRASTRUCTURES INC. SATELLITE, SURVEILLANCE & ENVIRONMENTAL SENSORS

Sensor networks coupled with associated cyber infrastructure offer a powerful combination of distributed sensing capacity, internet and satellite communication, and computational tools that lend themselves to countless applications in ecological research. Moreover, new designs of sensor networks allow the observation of systems in near-real time based on incoming data not only from local sources, but also from nested or adjacent networks and from remote sensing data streams. These advances are providing a new and better understanding of our ecological systems by revealing previously unobservable phenomena.²²¹

5.20.1 Background

Beginning with the early use of aerial photography, remote sensing has been recognised as a valuable tool for viewing, analyzing, characterising, and making decisions about the environment.²²² Remote sensing is the science of obtaining information about objects or areas

²¹⁶ Coombs, W. T., “Crisis management”, in W. T. Coombs (Ed.), *PSI handbook of business security: Securing the enterprise* (pp. 152-164). Westport, CT: Praeger Security International, 2008.

²¹⁷ Moskowitz, H., Drnevich, P., Ersoy, O., Altinkemer, K., & Chaturvedi, A., “Using real-time decision tools to improve distributed decision-making capabilities in high-magnitude crisis situations”, *Decision Sciences*, 42(2), 477-493, 2011, doi:10.1111/j.1540-5915.2011.00319.x

²¹⁸ Wojciechowicz, W., Zych, J., & Hotubowicz, W., “Information and communication technology and crisis management”, 2012, *Technical Sciences*, 15(1), 101-110.

²¹⁹ Patrick Bass, “The Role of Information Technology in Crisis Management”, 31 August 2014, <http://www.patrickwbass.com/onsecurity/academic-writings/>

²²⁰ “How to prevent your Facebook Account from being Hacked”, Facebook, <https://www.facebook.com/media/set/?set=a.209344199157315.47760.155945651163837&type=1>

²²¹ Philip W. Rundel, Eric A. Graham, Michael F. Allen, Jason C. Fisher and Thomas C. Harmon, “Environmental sensor networks in ecological research” 16 APR 2009, <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2009.02811.x/pdf>

²²² “Satellite Remote Sensing and its Role in Global Change Research”, CIESIN Thematic Guides <http://www.ciesin.org/TG/RS/RS-home.html>

from a distance, typically from aircraft or satellites. Remote sensors such as satellites collect data by detecting the energy that is reflected from Earth, in a passive or active fashion. Passive sensors respond to external stimuli, recording radiation reflected from Earth's surface, usually from the sun, during daylight hours. In contrast, active sensors use internal stimuli to collect data about the Earth.²²³ Satellite remote sensing is defined as the use of satellite-borne sensors to observe, measure, and record the electromagnetic radiation reflected or emitted by the Earth and its environment for subsequent analysis and extraction of information.²²⁴

Sensors and surveillance technologies encompass a wide range of devices, systems and practices used by law enforcement and criminal justice organisations to monitor and detect persons, locations, behaviors or features. These technologies are predominantly electronic or optical in nature, often interfaced with computer or human operating systems. The most well-known sensor and surveillance technology is the ubiquitous surveillance camera. However, modern sensor technologies have greatly expanded the options and tools available to security, police, corrections and investigative officers. Examples include infrared and low-light vision, body-worn cameras, chemical and biological detectors, and intelligent video surveillance.²²⁵ Generally, a sensor surveillance system consists of a set of wireless sensor nodes and a set of targets to be monitored. The sensors collaborate with each other to watch or monitor the targets and pass the sensed data to the base station. Power is by batteries on a stringent power budget.²²⁶

Environmental sensor networks offer a powerful combination of distributed sensing capacity, real-time data visualisation and analysis, and integration with adjacent networks and remote sensing data streams. Environmental sensor networks are already in operation and large new networks are planned for monitoring multiple habitats at many different scales. Projects range in spatial scale from continental systems designed to measure global change and environmental stability to those involved with the monitoring of only a few meters of forest edge in fragmented landscapes. More recently, complex sensors, such as networked digital cameras and microphones, as well as newly emerging sensors, are being integrated into sensor networks employing hierarchical methods of sensing. They carry the promise of a deeper understanding of our ecological systems by revealing previously unobservable phenomena.²²⁷

5.20.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

During the last decades remote sensing has become an operational tool in the disaster preparedness and warning phases for cyclones, droughts and floods. Remote sensing allows monitoring events during the time of occurrence. Additionally, it provides a data base from which the evidence left behind by disasters that have occurred before can be interpreted, and combined with other information to arrive at hazard maps, indicating which areas are

²²³ “What is remote sensing?”, National Oceanic and atmospheric administration, United States Department of Commerce <http://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/remotesensing.html>

²²⁴ “Satellite Remote Sensing and its Role in Global Change Research”, CIESIN Thematic Guides <http://www.ciesin.org/TG/RS/RS-home.html>

²²⁵ “Sensors & Surveillance Technologies”, Justnet :The website of National Law Enforcement and Corrections Technology Center, <https://justnet.org/sensors/index.html>

²²⁶ Hai Liu, Xiaohua Jia, Peng-Jun Wan, Chih-Wei Yi, S. Kami Makki, and Niki Pissinou, “Maximizing Lifetime of Sensor Surveillance Systems”, IEEE/ACM TRANSACTIONS ON NETWORKING, VOL. 15, NO. 2, APRIL 2007, <http://www.cs.cityu.edu.hk/~jia/research/ToN07.pdf>

²²⁷ Philip W. Rundel, Eric A. Graham, Michael F. Allen, Jason C. Fisher and Thomas C. Harmon, “Environmental sensor networks in ecological research” 16 APR 2009, <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2009.02811.x/pdf>

potentially dangerous. Satellite remote sensing is the ideal tool for disaster management, since it offers information over large areas, and at short time intervals. Although it can be utilised in the various phases of disaster management, such as prevention, preparedness, relief, and reconstruction, in practice it is mostly used for warning and monitoring. In the disaster relief phase, sensors are extremely useful in combination with satellite positioning systems (such as GPS) in search and rescue operations in areas that have been devastated and where it is difficult to orientate. The impact and departure of the disaster event leaves behind an area of immense devastation. Remote sensing can assist in damage assessment and aftermath monitoring, providing a quantitative base for relief operations.²²⁸ Sensors such as orbiting satellites, have access to the Internet and are capable of providing information that can be viewed using the Internet.²²⁹ In order to ensure the quick spread of news related to a disaster, sensors might in the future become able to transfer their information and provide automatic updates of such news using the social media networks. Thus, rumors would be avoided and the information would be reliable and valid.

5.21 SMART CITIES AND SMART TRANSPORTATION

Smart Cities are a future reality for municipalities around the world. These cities will use the power of ubiquitous communication networks, data analytics, cloud computing, highly distributed wireless sensor technology, and intelligent management systems to solve current and future challenges in order to return community quickly to normal.²³⁰

A Smart City is a place where the traditional networks and services are made more efficient with the use of digital and telecommunication technologies, for the benefit of its inhabitants and its businesses. In addition, it provides for smarter urban transport networks, upgraded water supply, a more interactive and responsive city administration and safer public spaces.²³¹

5.21.1 Background

In smart cities, digital technologies translate into better public services, better use of resources, less impact on the environment and a high quality of life.²³² Authorities in smart cities, are able to monitor air pollution concentration and its sources such as pollution emitted from cars and toxic gases generated. Additionally, they are able of detecting rubbish levels in containers to optimise the trash collection routes.²³³ Generally, a smart city is able to inform citizens about imminent risks and to provide vital information before, during and after disasters.

²²⁸ “Remote Sensing For Natural Disaster Management”, Cees Van Westen, International Institute for Aerospace Survey and Earth Sciences, ITC, The Netherlands, Division of Applied Geomorphological Surveys, http://www.isprs.org/proceedings/XXXIII/congress/part7/1609_XXXIII-part7.pdf

²²⁹ Nirupama, Slobodan S. Simonovic, “Role of Remote Sensing For Natural Disaster Management”, Prepared for: Institute of Catastrophic Loss Reduction, London, Ontario, July 2002, <http://ir.lib.uwo.ca/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1002&context=wrrr>

²³⁰ Ruthbea Yesner Clarke, “Smart Cities and the Internet of Everything: The Foundation of Delivering Next-Generation Citizen Services” Sponsored by Cisco, 2013, https://www.cisco.com/web/strategy/docs/scc/ioe_citizen_svcs_white_paper_idc_2013.pdf

²³¹ European Commission, “Smart Cities”, <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/about-smart-cities>

²³² Ibid

²³³ Jacob Morgan, “A Simple Explanation Of The Internet Of Things”, 13 May 2014, <http://www.forbes.com/sites/jacobmorgan/2014/05/13/simple-explanation-internet-things-that-anyone-can-understand/>

Intelligent transportation and telecommunications play a crucial role in disaster response and crisis management.²³⁴ Intelligent transportation relates to different modes of transport and traffic management and enables various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated, and ‘smarter’ use of transport networks.²³⁵ A smart transportation system is capable of rerouting traffic by using signals from Wi-Fi routers along roadways, keep track of vehicles and their location, and detect congestions and car accidents.²³⁶

5.21.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Smart city emergency management technologies integrate and analyze massive amounts of data to anticipate, mitigate, and even prevent risks during crises. Their emergency management solutions use sophisticated analytics engines to automatically process the data. This provides responders with data quality, not just data quantity.²³⁷

This data is leveraged, for example, to intelligently reroute traffic when highways and roads are in emergency because of a great disaster.²³⁸ Since social media have the ability to reach a large audience, as more people turn to social media to stay informed, it is the perfect go-to source for reporting information and provide pertinent data quickly and efficiently.²³⁹

5.22 SOCIAL MEDIA GOVERNANCE

With the new technologies, especially social media such as Facebook and Twitter, many new opportunities have arisen for public as well as private organisations to share their insights with their employees, members or external stakeholders. Consequently challenges haven arisen with regard to remaining in control about the information flow between individuals and across organisational boundaries.²⁴⁰ In turn this asks for guidelines and/or a framework regarding the usage of social media within organisations, or alternatively formulated for ‘social media governance’.

5.22.1 Background

²³⁴ Adel S. Elmaghraby, “Cyber security challenges in Smart Cities: Safety, security and privacy”, 2014, <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2090123214000290>

²³⁵ Mike Vargo, “More Than Smart Cars: It's Smart Transportation”, http://engineering.cmu.edu/alumni/magazine/winter_fall_2012/smart_cars_smart_transportation.html

²³⁶ Liz Enbysk, “How smart transportation systems reduce emergency response times, saves lives”, 9 April 2013, <http://smartcitiescouncil.com/article/how-smart-transportation-systems-reduce-emergency-response-times-saves-lives>

²³⁷ IBM, “Smarter Cities solutions for emergency management”, http://www.ibm.com/smarterplanet/us/en/public_safety/nextsteps/solution/M573313P64918R78.html

²³⁸ Ruthbea Yesner Clarke, “Smart Cities and the Internet of Everything: The Foundation of Delivering Next-Generation Citizen Services” Sponsored by Cisco, 2013, https://www.cisco.com/web/strategy/docs/scc/ioe_citizen_svcs_white_paper_idc_2013.pdf

²³⁹ Mary Guin, “The Link between Crisis Management and Social Media”, 9 April, 2014, <http://www2.agilityrecovery.com/the-link-between-crisis-management-and-social-media/>

²⁴⁰ McAfee, A.P. (2009). ‘Shattering the myths about enterprise 2.0’. *Harvard Business review*, 87(11), pp. 1-6.

For the purposes of this theme governance will be defined as “a mixture of hierarchical and non-hierarchical forms of coordination”.²⁴¹ This often results in structures where leaders, instead of prescribing certain behaviour, motivate followers to develop their own approach within a set boundaries, such as the prohibition of leaking confidential information. When applied to social media, governance thus can be seen as the coming together of formal and informal frameworks with the purpose of regulating the behaviour of group members within the social web.²⁴² Generally it is about regulating the communications therein between the organisation and its people, for example, communication with external stakeholders, whereby guidelines seem to play a major role.

5.22.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

Social media governance has no potential technical impact on crisis management, since it does not concern a new technological development. The relevance lies more in the need to find an overarching framework that regulates the use of new technologies (with regard to communications). A need that is maybe even more urgent with regard to the communication during crisis situations, where the information need is high while this information is dynamic, uncertain and unpredictable and communication can be difficult.²⁴³ To add even further to the complexity there is simultaneously a significant risk of information overload. Governance is needed to address questions and concerns regarding how to organise crisis communication efficiently and effectively resulting in the right information reaching the right people. This is especially important since risks regarding the dissemination of rumours and misinformation by citizens or non-professional organisations during crisis situations have increased.²⁴⁴

5.23 TOOLS FOR THE MEDIATION BETWEEN GOVERNMENTS AND CITIZENS

Modern network technologies offer the potential for enhancing communication between government agencies and citizens.²⁴⁵ Every technological innovation inherent in the digital era creates new linkages between governments and citizens, which play an important role in increasing confidence in states and governments by engaging citizens in public decision-making processes. This elevates ICTs, mainly the Internet, into a tool for communication between state and citizens.²⁴⁶

5.23.1 Background

²⁴¹ Zerfass, A., Fink, S. and Linke, A. (2011, March). “Social Media Governance: Regulatory frameworks as drivers of success in online communications”. Paper presented at the 14th Annual International Public Relations Research Conference, Miami, Florida, USA. pp.8

²⁴² Ibid.

²⁴³ Bharosa, N., Lee, J. & Janssen, M. (2010). “Challenges and obstacles in sharing and coordinating information during multi-agency disaster response: Propositions from field exercises”. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 12(1), pp. 1-7. DOI 10.1007/s10796-009-9174-z

²⁴⁴ Sutton, J., Palen, L. and Shklovski, I. (2008). “Backchannels on the Front Lines: Emergent Uses of Social Media in the 2007 Southern California Wildfires”. In: F. Fiedrich, F. and B. Van de Walle (eds.), *Proceedings of the 5th International ISCRAM Conference*. Washington, DC, USA.

²⁴⁵ “E-Mail Communication Between Government and Citizens”, C. Richard Neu, Robert H. Anderson, Tora K. Bikson http://www.rand.org/pubs/issue_papers/IP178/index2.html

²⁴⁶ “Bridging the gap between local governments and citizens :Do web sites matter for creating covnerance? Some observations on Turkish local governments”, Tanju Tosun, Gulgun Erdogan TosunI <http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/nispacee/unpan027503.pdf>

At the beginning of the new millennium, governments had to reconcile two important points. One of them is developments in new ICTs. The other is a decline in citizens' confidence in public authorities.²⁴⁷ In order to reinforce citizens' confidence, many governments around the world improved their communication channels. For example, the Norwegian government has set up an objective of making everyday life simpler for its citizens and supports a knowledge society where everyone can participate and where the potential use of ICT is optimised and where public authorities are a safe and efficient distributor of services and resources.²⁴⁸

In recent years, Wuhu City, China, has witnessed rapid social and economic development. However, some new social issues and conflicts are also emerging. The Wuhu municipal government sought a new forum for soliciting citizen feedback and opinions. The municipality chose the Internet as the most convenient way to reform through citizen participation. In January 2003, the Wuhu City Government began the "Citizen's Hopes" (Shiminxincheng) chat room on its website to collect resident suggestions and concerns. The government now publicises numerous topics related to economic development, social affairs, and governmental operations to guide citizens' discussion and participation. In order to sustain public interest in the forum, Wuhu officials have also committed to answering every complaint or question posted to the site.²⁴⁹

5.23.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

New challenges and opportunities deriving from new ICT tools can be seen as a transformation agent in the relationship between state and its citizens.²⁵⁰ Changing the relationship between citizens and government is often cited as a goal for digital government and new tools such as social media have the potential to improve interactions with citizens through dialogue and greater transparency.²⁵¹

Social media are incredibly important in emergency situations and offer an outlet for real-time, instant communication with the public. Government managers in charge of social media channels ought to have a seat in emergency operation centers, helping to integrate communication efforts with other government functions and being a direct part of the response effort. Government-run social media are able to broadcast corrections to misinformation, create an official hash tag to distinguish information on the emergency situation, and respond to social media users sharing out-of-date information.²⁵² To illustrate

²⁴⁷ Tanju Tosun, Gulgun Erdogan Tosun1, "Bridging the gap between local governments and citizens: Do web sites matter for creating governance? Some observations on Turkish local governments",

<http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/nispacee/unpan027503.pdf>

²⁴⁸ Kari Strande, "e-Government for e-Citizens – NSDI as Tools in Good Governance. Examples from eNorway and Norway Digital 1", Norway, International Federation of Surveyors Article of the Month – November 2008,

http://www.fig.net/pub/monthly_articles/november_2008/november_2008_strande.pdf

²⁴⁹ Ma Jun, "Internet-Mediated Interactions between Government and Citizens", Harvard University Kennedy School of Government, 2006 Winner Innovation Award,

<http://www.innovations.harvard.edu/awards.html?id=31071>

²⁵⁰ Tanju Tosun, Gulgun Erdogan Tosun1, "Bridging the gap between local governments and citizens: Do web sites matter for creating governance? Some observations on Turkish local governments",

<http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/nispacee/unpan027503.pdf>

²⁵¹ Karen Mossberger, Yonghong Wu, Jared Crawford, "Connecting Citizens and Local Governments? Social Media and Interactivity in Major U.S. Cities", Presented at Public Management Research Conference, Madison, June 21, 2013, and the references therein,

<http://www.union.wisc.edu/pmra2013/Paper%20Submissions/New/Connecting%20Citizens%20and%20Local%20Governments%20Social%20Media%20and%20Interactivity%20in%20Major%20US%20Cities.pdf>

²⁵² "8 Ways for Government to Engage Citizens with Social Media", Mary Yang March 6th, 2012

<http://www.govdelivery.com/blog/2012/03/8-ways-for-government-to-engage-citizens-with-social-media/>

the point, there are many examples of the two-way communication between government and citizens abundant in all COSMIC deliverables. Here we add two more:

- FEMA officials were able to monitor social media conversations and respond to tornado disaster reports in Joplin, Mo., by receiving information from citizens on the ground before official reports could be verified
- in Boulder, Colorado, real-time social communications between citizens and government through Facebook and Twitter helped save lives and property as a wildfire raged in 2010.²⁵³

5.24 TOOLS FOR TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY

More and more (government) services are offered online, to enhance quality and responsiveness, while simultaneously offering increased insight in the process and its progress. The result is greater transparency, which is a necessary, however not sufficient requisite for accountability.²⁵⁴ A very prominent development is that of e-government, where concurrent technological developments offer new and direct ways to communicate with a government or government-related business and empower civilians.

5.24.1 Background

The advances of the Internet and ICT have increased possibilities for transparency and accountability by substantially diminishing the costs of collecting, distributing and accessing information.²⁵⁵ Especially the new technological possibilities have greatly increased the ways governments and corporations can offer information to the public, but also to their (public) employees and customers and how these, in return, can communicate about this information. Simultaneously, fora, such as social media, offer employees and civilians a platform to immediately publish relevant information (about governments and corporations) and even organise action accordingly. Consequently, it has become more difficult for traditionally dominant powers, such as the state to control the discourse, since there have arisen so many communication venues besides the traditional media. The 2007 election of a new Australian Prime Minister and the aftermath of the 2009 Iranian election are examples of how respectively blogs and Twitter provided civilians with a venue to air a contrasting ‘opinion’.²⁵⁶ The success of the latter also demonstrates that only a few have to use a medium of this sort for the message to carry far: other influencers can distribute it independently of the originator.

5.24.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

The possibilities for emergency response services and efforts to be transparent and accountable are greatly enhanced with the new technologies, as shown during Hurricane

²⁵³ “America’s Town Hall Moves Online”, Stephen J. Rohleder, October 3, 2012,

[HTTP://ALLTHINGSD.COM/20121003/AMERICAS-TOWN-HALL-MOVES-ONLINE/](http://allthingsd.com/20121003/americas-town-hall-moves-online/)

²⁵⁴ Halachmi, A. and Greiling, D. (2013). “Transparency, E-government and Accountability: Some Issues and Considerations”, *Public Performance & Management Review*, 36(4), pp. 562–584.

²⁵⁵ Roberts, A. (2006) quoted in: Bertot, J.C., Jaeger, P.T. and Grimes, J.M. (2010). “Using ICTs to create a culture of transparency: E-government and social media as openness and anti-corruption tools for societies”. *Government Information Quarterly*, 27, pp. 264–271.

²⁵⁶ Bertot, J.C., Jaeger, P.T. and Grimes, J.M. (2010). Using ICTs to create a culture of transparency: E-government and social media as openness and anti-corruption tools for societies. *Government Information Quarterly*, 27, pp. 264–271.

Sandy.²⁵⁷ Especially social media such as Twitter or Facebook enable more freely available reports on, and insight in (ongoing) emergency response activities, partially by enabling emergency responders to communicate directly with the public. Status updates and reassurance messages that emergency response efforts are “on the way” or “under control” and (trained) professionals are on the disaster site can flow freely and without being subjected to filtering by the traditional media with regard to content and/or timing and frequency of distribution. Subsequently however, this transparency can also lead to increased vulnerability to public scrutiny and criticism as happened with the Long Beach Township Police Departments’ (LBTPD) performance during Sandy. The LBTPD let itself be held publicly accountable by posting to and answering questions on the highly public and persistent forum Facebook. They continued this behaviour even when comments from residents increasingly started expressing critique and negative sentiment.²⁵⁸

5.25 USER GENERATED CONTENT & ICT FOR CREATIVITY AND EXPRESSION

Much of the online content essential for activities like data mining, open data and big data, as discussed in previous paragraphs, comes from ‘non-professional’ users. Such data is called User Generated Content (UGC) and has been available more abundantly by the day ever since the advent of Web 2.0. This entailed the transition of the Internet from a medium in which most people are just consumers passively viewing content, to a highly interactive medium where people collaborate and interact with each other by adding to content, discussing it, valuing it and engaging in other similar activities.

5.25.1 Background

There is no strict and widely accepted definition of User Generated Content (USG), possibly due to the ongoing development of these phenomena. Often however it is described as content for online mediums that is created by (unpaid) users, with the addition that this content is dynamic: it can be added on to, rated or recommended. In addition the OECD describes three characteristics that can help define UGC.²⁵⁹ Firstly, by requiring that the content is *published* in some way, though the publicity may be restricted to a limited group of people, email, bilateral instant messages and so forth are effectively excluded. Furthermore, own value must be added to the content, by displaying a certain amount of *creative effort*, which may be collaborative, while creating or adapting content. For example by uploading own photographs, expressing thoughts in a blog or creating music clips. Conversely, uploading a copy of a television broadcast is not an example of *creative effort*. Lastly USG is normally *not created within professional routines or practises*. Often users seek to connect with peers, to express themselves or just in search for fame, notoriety or prestige, mostly without expecting or intending remuneration or profit. That said, recently, increasingly users do turn into professionals and receive remuneration; this results in USG being made marketable.

²⁵⁷ Hughes, A.L., Denis, St. L.A., Palen, L. and Anderson, K.M. (2014). “Online Public Communications by Police & Fire Services during the 2012 Hurricane Sandy”. Proceedings of the ACM 2014 Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2014). doi: 10.1145/2556288.2557227

²⁵⁸ Ibid.

²⁵⁹ OECD, Directorate for Science, Technology and Industry, Committee for Information, Computer and Communications Policy (2006). *Participative Web: User-Created Content* (DSTI/ICCO/IE(2006)7/FINAL). Retrieved October, 22, 2014 <http://www.oecd.org/sti/38393115.pdf>

What these characteristics show is that UGC often is not intended to share news in the strict sense of the word as such. Nevertheless there are instances, such as crises, where users communicate relevant information through mediums based on USG, such as Facebook, Twitter or YouTube. Information that is immediately available, disseminated quickly and can be uploaded, but also added onto by anybody, much in contradiction with traditional media. Facebook for example turned out to be essential in the communication of the well-being and whereabouts of students during the Virginia Tech shooting.²⁶⁰ This even led to the compilation of victim lists on several social media, that together correctly identified all the victims before the official list was released by the university. In the Southern Californian wildfires of 2007 social media provided a venue through which people in the affected areas could extract locally relevant information. Alternative news sources, individual blogs, twitter, photo-sharing sites and group discussions were all used to either post and discuss or more commonly receive information.

5.25.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

The previously discussed cases show that UGC can have added value in crisis management. UGC-platforms can provide an important medium to communicate and learn relevant information for civilians as well as professionals in emergency services, like fire services, police and EMS. This is not only about the (own) well-being and whereabouts, but also about dynamic situation reports, what (not) to do lists and so on. For example after an overextension of the emergency line during Hurricane Sandy, Twitter was used to send emergency ‘calls’.²⁶¹ Nevertheless, there are also limits and obstacles to this potential. A case study in the Netherlands on the use of Twitter as medium for governments to spread and receive new information during the ‘Moerdijk chemical fire’ has found that no new and relevant information was published by civilians or governments. Moreover, there is a hazard for governmental tweets to be buried underneath citizen questions and emotional exclamations.²⁶² Still, in addition to being immediately available, quickly disseminated and more or less publicly open for contribution, UGC-platforms can provide highly locally specific and relevant information from and to specific communities, such as *Community Emergency Response Teams (CERT)*.²⁶³ They can also provide people with inside information or know-how, based on experience with a medium to spread this information, whereas others can help communication through publishing lists with contact information, for example e-mail addresses.

5.26 VISUALISATION – INFORMATION, KNOWLEDGE, VISUAL ANALYTICS

Information visualisation (IV) is a rapidly growing field that emerged from research in human-computer interaction, computer science, graphics, visual design, psychology, and business methods. Information visualisation is increasingly applied as a critical component in scientific research, digital libraries, data mining, financial data analysis, and manufacturing

²⁶⁰ Palen, L. (2008). ‘‘Online Social Media in Crisis Events’’. *Edu cause Quarterly*, 3, pp.76-78.

²⁶¹ Hughes, A.L., Denis, St. L.A., Palen, L. and Anderson, K. (2014). ‘‘Online Public Communications by Police & Fire Services during the 2012 Hurricane Sandy’’. Proceedings of CHI 2014, ACM Press.

²⁶² Helsloot, I and Groenendaal, J. (2013). ‘‘Twitter: an Underutilized Potential during Sudden Crises?’’. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 21(3), pp. 178-183.

²⁶³ Brennan, M.A. and Flint, C.G. (2007). ‘‘Uncovering the hidden dimensions of rural disaster mitigation: capacity building through community emergency response teams’’. *Southern rural sociology*, 22(2), pp. 111-126.

production control.²⁶⁴ IV explores the use of computer-supported interactive graphical representations to explain data and amplify cognition. It provides a means to communicate ideas or facts about the data, to validate hypotheses and to facilitate the discovery of new facts via exploration.²⁶⁵

5.26.1 Background

Whilst IV focuses on the use of computer-based tools to explore large data sets, Knowledge Visualisation (KV) investigates how to create and transfer insights between individuals within groups, how to manage and reduce complexity to allow understanding, and how to support learning, communication and interaction through new approaches and techniques. Knowledge Visualisation aims to facilitate the transfer of facts, insights, experiences, values, expectations, perspectives, opinions and predictions. Researchers and practitioners in the domains of Knowledge Visualisation, develop strategies, tools and methods to make knowledge visible and to improve processes through which knowledge can be identified, accessed, assessed, shared, discussed, applied and generally managed.²⁶⁶

Visual analytics (VA) was initially proposed as a means to help United States intelligence analysts meet the challenge of dealing with the masses of security-related information made available to them following the terrorist attacks on September 11, 2001, on the World Trade Center and Pentagon. Visual analytics is defined as “the science of analytical reasoning facilitated by interactive visual interfaces.”²⁶⁷ It is a multidisciplinary field intended to help people understand how to synthesise information in order to derive insights from massive, dynamic, ambiguous, and often conflicting data. In practice, it helps skilled analysts to rapidly explore large, complex data sets to gain new insights using interactive visualisations. It draws upon research in a number of relevant areas, including information visualisation, human computer interaction, machine learning, statistics, and cognitive science.²⁶⁸

Although visual analytics originally was intended to solve data analysis problems in the security and intelligence domains, the tools and techniques that have been developed in the past 6-8 years are also of great interest to analysts in many other data-rich domains, e.g., aerospace safety, manufacturing and maintenance, transportation, financial risk analysis and fraud detection, business intelligence and process analysis, health care and medical research, and environmental health and safety.²⁶⁹

5.26.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

²⁶⁴ Morgan Kaufmann, “The Craft of Information Visualization: Readings and Reflections”, April, 2003, <http://www.cs.umd.edu/hcil/pubs/books/craft.shtml>

²⁶⁵ Riccardo Mazza, “Introduction to Information Visualization”, April, 2, 2009, <http://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Information-Visualization-Riccardo-Mazza/dp/1848002181>

²⁶⁶ 8th International Symposium Knowledge Visualization and Visual Thinking, KV2012 <http://www.graphicslink.co.uk/IV2012/KV.htm>

²⁶⁷ Thomas, J.J. & Cook, K.A. (Eds)., “Illuminating the path: The research and development agenda for visual analytics”, IEEE Computer Society, 2005, posted on Vancouver institute for visual analytics, 6 April 2014, <http://www.viva-viva.ca/index.php/about/about-va>

²⁶⁸ Ibid.

²⁶⁹ Keim, D.A. & Mansmann, F. Schneidewind, J. & Ziegler, H., “Challenges in Visual Data Analysis”, Proceedings of Information Visualization (IV), IEEE, p.9-16, 2006, posted on 06 April 2014, Vancouver institute for visual analytics, <http://www.viva-viva.ca/index.php/about/about-va>

Visualisations of storm forecasts offer opportunities to improve risk awareness and communication of impending disaster in emergency situations such as a hurricane evacuation. A continuum of potential visualisations ranges from static maps, animated model output, 3-D, immersive, and multimedia. In addition to risk communication aimed at the public, high-quality photorealistic geo-visualisations might allow managers to investigate and explore forecasted surges and could reveal vulnerabilities and improve preparedness and response.²⁷⁰ Social media offer useful preparedness information and the latest updates on emergency events. For example, the organisation “Centers for Disease Control and Prevention”²⁷¹ (CDC) uses Twitter and Facebook to provide latest information on emergencies, preparedness tips, and real-time updates and health alerts for the public during an emergency.²⁷² Social media is often seen as an ephemeral medium but as reporting on Hurricane Sandy showed, it is a treasure trove that helps plan and forecast for future disasters.²⁷³ A Twitter Visualisation tool such as “Sentiment Viz: Tweet Sentiment Visualisation” is capable of collecting tweets and visualise them in numerous ways. Tweets are presented using several different visualisation techniques. Each technique is designed to highlight different aspects of the tweets and their sentiment. The “timeline” feature visualises when tweets were posted and the “tweets tab” feature shows the date, author and body of each tweet visualising its sentiment in green and blue.²⁷⁴ Such features allow the application to provide an overview of disaster-related topics and improve the preparedness phase of imminent disasters.

5.27 WEARABLE SENSORS AND SENSORS INTEGRATED IN MOBILE COMMUNICATION DEVICES

The terms “wearable technology”, “wearable devices”, and “wearables” refer to electronic technologies or computers incorporated into clothing and accessories. These wearable devices perform many of the same computing tasks as mobile phones and laptop computers. In some cases, wearable technology outperforms these hand-held devices. Wearable technology tends to be more sophisticated than hand-held technology today because it provides sensory and scanning abilities not seen in mobile and laptop devices.²⁷⁵

5.27.1 Background

Combining wearable technology with computing devices and other sensors enhances the potential of IT solutions. “Sensors have been an important addition to smart-phones ever since accelerometers were first used to determine screen orientation. Now a wide variety of sensors, including magnetometers, barometers, and gyroscopes, are found in many other devices.”²⁷⁶

²⁷⁰ Thomas R. Allen, Stephen Sanchagrin, George McLeod, “Visualization for Hurricane Storm Surge Risk Awareness and Emergency Communication”, <http://www.intechopen.com/books/approaches-to-disaster-management-examining-the-implications-of-hazards-emergencies-and-disasters/visualization-for-hurricane-storm-surge-risk-awareness-and-emergency-communication>

²⁷¹ <http://emergency.cdc.gov/socialmedia/>

²⁷² “Emergency Preparedness and Response”, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, <http://emergency.cdc.gov/socialmedia/>

²⁷³ Matthew Yeomans, “Social media's crucial role in disaster relief efforts”, *Guardian Professional*, 6 November 2012, <http://www.theguardian.com/sustainable-business/social-media-hurricane-sandy-emergency-planners>

²⁷⁴ Healey C., Ramaswamy S., “Visualizing Twitter Sentiment”, 28 December 2013, http://www.csc.ncsu.edu/faculty/healey/tweet_viz/

²⁷⁵ Tehrani, Kiana, and Andrew Michael. “Wearable Technology and Wearable Devices: Everything You Need to Know.” *Wearable Devices Magazine*, WearableDevices.com, March 2014,

<http://www.wearabledevices.com/what-is-a-wearable-device/>

²⁷⁶ Jim Steele, “Integrating sensors into mobile devices”, 30 April 2013,

Wearable technology allows the wearer access to real time information: the sensors, included in wearable devices are capable of taking photos and synchronise with other devices, for example mobiles. Data-input capabilities and local storage are features of such devices. Examples of wearable devices include watches, glasses, contact lenses, e-textiles and smart fabrics, headbands, beanies and caps, jewelry such as rings, bracelets, and hearing aid-like devices designed to look like earrings.²⁷⁷

5.27.2 Potential technical impact on crisis management

During disasters, rescue and response teams can use wearable sensors to provide information about their location and the prevailing situations. Capturing information about the status of the environment is critical in crisis response, e.g. in case of earthquake, overcrowding, and flooding. Captured information might include for example: location of injured and number of those rescued; and data from the environment such as temperature and air quality. Information is needed to support cooperation during crisis response and to inform post-crisis debriefings about what happened and to learn lessons from mistakes made.²⁷⁸ Nevertheless most of the times, disasters occur unexpectedly, thus prohibiting the wider public to have access to wearable sensor facilities. On the other hand, social media users themselves might operate as sensors which transmit useful location information by capturing images and posting them, thus aiding response teams.

<http://www.ecnmag.com/articles/2013/04/integrating-sensors-mobile-devices>

²⁷⁷ Tehrani Kiana, and Andrew Michael, “Wearable Technology and Wearable Devices: Everything You Need to Know.” *Wearable Devices Magazine*, WearableDevices.com, March 2014

<http://www.wearabledevices.com/what-is-a-wearable-device/>

²⁷⁸ “WATCHiT: Towards wearable data collection in crisis management” TEI 2014, Feb 2014, Munich, Germany, <http://www.tei-conf.org/14/wip/wip-mora.pdf>

6 CONCLUSION

As we have documented in other reports of COSMIC (D1.1, D1.2, D2.1, D2.2), new communication technologies and social media have already greatly impacted crisis management, with concrete evidence existing of their important role in a large number of major disasters and incidents. The discussion and analysis in this report builds on project's previous conclusions and has shown two major trends.

- First, the impact of new communication technologies and social media is expected to grow continuously in importance and extent. More people are using these technologies, the level of official reliance on them is growing, more resources, especially data resources, are being devoted, and ever more opportunities appear for exploiting them in the context of crisis management.
- Second, a wider spectrum of technologies – not necessarily belonging to the sphere of communication – is expected to become increasingly important for communication during crisis management. For example, as the amount of information being communicated continues to increase in size, it becomes impossible for the human mind to process it all: technologies that organise, analyse and present information in a human-friendly form will become integral components of the communication process.

New technologies and social media have greatly expanded the overall scope of communication in crisis management, due to several new synergetic factors, such as access to technology, richer communication modalities, communication occurring in public, and data exhaust. This scope today encompasses intentional acts of communication, unintentional acts of communication, handling information as its recipient, and accessing and analysing public information as a third party. We have identified 27 distinct emerging technology and application areas which are relevant with respect to this scope. These include: citizen journalism, cloud, crowdsourcing, data mining, big data, decision support, open data, Internet of Things, wearable sensors and others. A summary of their appraisal for their possible role in social media aided crisis management is shown in the table below.

Table 2. Potential impact of technology and application areas in crisis management

Technology/application area		Potential technical impact on crisis management
1	citizen journalism	An “application area” rather than a “technology area”, with no immediate technical impact on crisis management, but with great functionality-increase potential for social media
2	cloud	It enhances social media access to applications, the combination of services and the reliability of the Internet infrastructure during crises.
3	crowdsourcing	Not a technology area, with no immediate technical impact on crisis management, which enriches social media with organisational resources available on a crisis
4	data mining and big data	A very important area as involves the monitoring and understanding of the full body of public, openly available communication information.
5	decision support	During crises, it supports scenario formulation, risk assessment, risk management, and communication towards responders and the public
6	e-inclusion & e-accountability	Not a technology area as such, but a best practice area, where crisis managers should be aware of their responsibility towards the social fabric and of the possibilities that the gap of e-inclusion may prevent social media messages reaching everybody during a crisis.
7	early warning systems	Social media may operate as an early warning system which assists crisis management especially at the response phase. As they announce valuable information, they are capable of alerting not only the public but also an organisation to an emerging problem.

8	epidemiology and prediction	As a result of the fear of an infectious disease, a crowd of worried citizens, with symptoms similar to the real symptoms of the infectious disease, will manifest itself. This form of citizen journalism can be used by governments to get insight in the way in which individuals and communities are coping with the effects of the epidemic.
9	integration of heterogeneous data	Social media might be considered as a heterogeneous database on which an integrated data system can potentially extract information related to natural disasters, diseases, terrorism and other types of crisis. Technical progress to achieve this is still ongoing here.
10	internet of things	In an ideal IoT world, devices can sense the forthcoming crisis signals and automatically inform several organisations and (possibly) the public (via alerts on social media), thus requiring no direct human meditation.
11	mobile eHealth	Mobile applications such as iWander can collect and evaluate using network techniques vital data to determine the condition of a patient and to act automatically for safe navigation, notification of caregivers, and emergency assistance calls.
12	natural language technologies	They potentially “understand” messages, track sentiment and tag text as positive, negative or neutral resulting in characterisations of posts of high importance during crises.
13	open data	Although still limited by proprietary policies, tools supporting open data have appeared. For example opendatakit, a set of tools to help organisations author, field, and manage mobile data collection solutions, which can then be published and exploited in support of crisis management.
14	“organic” or smartphone sensor networks	They enable the measurement of physical environmental conditions which can help situational awareness about the status of disaster-affected individuals and regions. As the sensing capabilities of smartphones expand, so will the potential value of networks of such devices, under the provision that privacy issues are resolved.
15	pattern analysis and machine intelligence	Artificial Intelligence for Disaster Response (AIDR) platforms are in existence today, ultimately aiming to leverage machine learning for automatic identification of informative meaningful content on social networks during disasters.
16	profiling social media users	Profiling lets crisis professionals know which groups of people can be reached by different social media platforms and direct information towards them during a crisis.
17	reporting and alerts services	This results in useful applications that offer a venue for emergency response officials to report an incident, accompanied by relevant information, and which subsequently notify other emergency response officials and organisations. An example in the Dutch NL-Alert.
18	robots and drones	Robots and drones can act and monitor without human presence in dangerous rescue situations. Being connected to the Internet, they can post information and photographs from the scene of the disaster on social media and help situational awareness of citizens and professionals alike.
19	secure communications and trustworthy ICT	Social media can be considered as reasonably trustworthy in crises due to security features implemented by most platforms, and by the fact that they are enhanced by the empowerment of other users to report malicious activities.
20	sensor infrastructures inc. satellite, surveillance & environmental sensors	In order to ensure the quick spread of news related to a disaster, remote sensors might in the future become able to transfer their information and provide automatic updates of such news using the social media networks. Thus, rumors would be avoided and the information would be reliable and valid.
21	smart cities and smart transportation	Ideally, a smart city is able to inform citizens about imminent risks and to provide vital information before, during and after disasters. A smart transportation system of the future will be able to reroute traffic – especially in emergencies – by using signals from routers along roadways, keep track of vehicles and their location, and detect congestions and car accidents.
22	social media governance	Social media governance has no potential technical impact on crisis management, since it does not concern a new technological development. Governance is needed, however, to address questions and concerns regarding how to organise crisis communication efficiently and effectively resulting in the right (not distorted) information reaching the right people.
23	tools for the mediation between	Government managers in charge of social media channels ought to have a seat in emergency operation centers, helping to integrate communication efforts with other

	governments and citizens	government functions and being a direct part of the response effort.
24	tools for transparency and accountability	Status updates and reassurance messages that emergency response efforts are “on the way” or “under control” and (trained) professionals are on the disaster site can flow freely on social platforms and without being subjected to filtering by the traditional media with regard to content and/or timing and frequency of distribution.
25	user generated content & ICT for creativity and expression	User-Generated Content (UGC) platforms are an important medium to communicate and learn relevant information for civilians as well as professionals in emergency services, covering people’s well-being and whereabouts, dynamic situation reports, what (not) to do lists and others.
26	visualisation – information, knowledge, visual analytics	Social media is often seen as an ephemeral medium but their visualisation facilities, such as Twitter’s “Sentiment Viz” can collect messages and visualise them in numerous ways, highlighting different aspects and sentiment. These can provide overviews of disaster-related communication and even improve preparedness.
27	wearable sensors and sensors integrated in mobile communication devices	Although rescue and response teams can use wearable sensors to provide information about their location and the prevailing situations, one has to note that disasters usually occur unexpectedly, thus prohibiting the wider public to have access to wearable sensor facilities. On the other hand, social media users themselves might operate as sensors which transmit useful location information by capturing images and posting them, thus aiding response teams.

As seen by the table above, emerging technology areas affect and potentially transform many aspects of crisis management. Coupled with social media, they contribute to the openness, fairness and quickness of communication during a crisis and can be used in a variety of ways: making diagnoses of vulnerabilities in systems and infrastructures (in preparation for crises); facilitating and simplifying search and rescue missions (during a crisis); and enhancing control and community connectedness (including the recovery stages after a crisis).

Finally, it must be noted that new and emerging technologies also entail a variety of risks, such as those to individuals’ privacy and sense of identity; the correct allocation of responsibility in evolving crises; the possibility of information overload; the potential of creating conflicts of interest among responders; and the general possibility of producing unintended, negative consequences even when the initial aim is crisis management.